
D6.3 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan, (updated version)

31 / 10 / 2025

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ABBREVIATIONS

BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
DCEP	Dissemination, communication and exploitation Plan
DCP	Dissemination and Communication plan
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EPC	European Patent Convention
ER	Exploitable Results
FG	Foreground
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
iLUC	Indirect land use change impacts of biofuels
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
M	Milestone
NDA	Non-disclosure agreement
NGOs	Non-governmental Organization
PR	Project Result
R&D	Research and Development
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SMA s	Social Media Accounts
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organization
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction to CARINA

CARINA is a cross-national 4-year long Innovation Action (01/11/2022- 31/10/2026), supported by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe programme.

The project focuses on new sustainable and diversified farming systems including 2 new oilseed crops, carinata and camelina, able to provide multiple low iLUC feedstocks for the bio-based economy. CARINA will demonstrate that increasing the diversification of cropping systems by adopting a well-thought and effective crop combination will enhance yield stability, farmers' revenue and the overall sustainability of farming systems, and, at the same time, to supplement the bioeconomy sector.

To facilitate the deployment of innovative systems, CARINA will also address certification issues of low iLUC feedstocks intended for bio-based industry. 9 Lighthouses, 5 Living Labs, and 9 Policy Innovation Labs will be established across Europe playing a leading role in the co-creation of CARINA innovation actions.

CARINA capitalizes on a highly experienced team of 19 partners, +5 affiliated entities, from 13 EU and Associated Countries (Italy, France, Spain, Germany, Greece, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Poland, UK, Serbia, Tunisia, Morocco, Switzerland).

Coordinator: ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA

PARTNERS	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
ALMA MATER STUDIORUM - UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA	UNIBO	IT
ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL	ARVALIS	FR
AGRAREN UNIVERSITET - PLOVDIV	AUP	BG
CAMELINA COMPANY ESPANA SL	CCE	ES
CENTRE FOR RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES AND SAVING FONDATION	CRES	EL
DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
FLANAT RESEARCH ITALIA SRL	FLANAT	IT
INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH IN THE DRY AREAS	ICARDA	LB

INSTITUT ZA RATARSTVO I POVRTARSTVO INSTITUT OD NACIONALNOG ZNACAJA ZA REPUBLIKU SRBIJU	IFVNCS	RS
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE DE TUNISIE	INRAT	TN
NOVAMONT SPA	NVMT	IT
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PEDAL	SK
UNIWERSYTET PRZYRODNICZY W POZNANIU	PULS	PL
SAIPOL	SAIPOL	FR
COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ESPANA U DE COOP SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA	SPANISH CO-OPS	ES
COOPERATIVAS AGRO-ALIMENTARIAS DE ANDALUCIA	FAECA	ES
FEDERACIÓN ARAGONESA DE COOPERATIVAS AGRARIAS	FACA	ES
UNION REGIONAL DE COOPERATIVAS AGRARIAS DE CASTILLA Y LEON	URCACYL	ES
COOPERATIVAS AGROALIMENTARIAS CASTILLA LA MANCHA UNION DE COOPERATIVAS	CACLM	ES
FEDERACIO DE COOPERATIVES AGRARIES DE CATALUNYA	FCAC	ES
TERRES INOVIA	TI	FR
KIMITEC BIOGROUP SL	KIMITEC	ES
RSB ROUNDTABLE ON SUSTAINABLE BIOMATERIALS ASSOCIATION	RSB	CH
NUSEED EUROPE LTD	NUSEED	UK

2. Objectives

The initial document, titled **D6.1 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, 1st version** elaborated within the framework of the **CARINA** project which is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under Grant Agreement No. 101081839. The current document titled **D6.3 - Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan, updated version (DCE)** presents developments and updates at this stage of the project.

In this context, the **main objectives** of the DCE offered partners a set of guidelines, responsibilities and timelines on how/when/where to disseminate the project, as well as to encourage them to use their channels (corporate websites, social networks, etc) to support the dissemination, with the main goal of gathering the ideal conditions to:

- Raise awareness of the project activities and events;
- Communicate and disseminate the findings and results among CARINA target groups;
- Identify and use the right channels to efficiently communicate with the target groups and stakeholders (including the identification of events, social media networks, press releases, multiplier organisations, etc.).
- Produce the necessary supporting material to ensure an effective dissemination, including printed material (i.e. brochure, poster, roll-up, goodies...) and digital materials (videos, infographics...).
- Create a link to other existing projects within the same scope;
- Facilitate regular communication, through press releases and newsletters, to inform about the latest news and developments of the project to the media;
- Plan, organise and monitor project's dissemination activities and events (new);
- Support the visibility and engagement activities of CARINA's project (new);
- Store all project's key outcomes and results on CARINA's website (new);
- Disseminate key outcomes and results through CARINA's SMAs (new);
- Promote open access to CARINA's deliverables and data (new).

In addition, CARINA partners focus on producing results that will be sustainable after the project's completion and ensuring that innovative ideas, methodologies, and results of the project will be fully identified, preserved and considered in terms of wider availability to all relevant stakeholders and, where applicable, commercialization potential. Thus, the consortium defines basic principles, from the early stages of the project, that will yield a solid management framework for the Background (BG), as well as the Foreground (FG) Intellectual Property Rights of CARINA.

The CARINA DCE plan sets the ground for monitoring the protection of IP and IPR within the consortium, which eventually will support the creation of value as regards the exploitable results of the project and facilitate successful innovation.

The primary aim of D6.1 was to identify the project's key assets and establish a foundation for defining their Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). It also aimed to create a shared understanding of the framework for exploiting these assets after the project concludes. In addition, the document outlined clear, practical objectives that enabled effective monitoring and the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication activities throughout the project. As the CARINA project progressed over its 36-month duration, new objectives were introduced to address emerging needs. These objectives provide clarity on why the Dissemination and Communication Plan is necessary. A summary of the existing and new objectives is provided above.

Five new objectives have been added to the DCE. The first two focus on supporting all engagement and dissemination efforts within the CARINA project. This includes activities such as creating tailored dissemination materials and drafting articles to highlight and promote important events like training sessions, Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Social Innovation Labs. The second new objective is centered on archiving the project's key outcomes and results on the CARINA website. The third objective aims at disseminating these results through the project's social media accounts (SMAs). Lastly, the final objective focuses on promoting open access to CARINA deliverables and data if not restricted.

3. Structure

The first chapters provide a general introduction to the CARINA project and outline the overall objectives of the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan. The document is structured to ensure a clear presentation of the strategic approach, tools, and processes supporting the effective dissemination, communication, and exploitation of project results.

The DCE Plan is divided into two main parts: Dissemination and Communication (Chapters 4 to 9) and Exploitation (Chapter 10):

Part I – Dissemination and Communication (Chapters 4–9)

This part presents CARINA's overall approach to dissemination and communication, setting out the strategic framework, objectives, target audiences, and implementation methods applied throughout the project. It explains how the consortium communicates project progress and outcomes, raises awareness among different stakeholder groups, and supports engagement and knowledge transfer.

Chapter 4 – Dissemination and Communication Plan

This chapter defines the overall dissemination and communication strategy, including objectives, guiding principles, and target audiences. It outlines the main communication tools and channels used by the consortium to ensure broad outreach and consistent visibility of the project. The chapter also includes a description of the CARINA website as the main digital dissemination platform, newsletters, social media activities, press releases, and promotional video. Together, these tools ensure that project information and results are effectively shared with relevant stakeholders, the scientific community, and the general public.

Chapter 5 – Promotional Materials

This chapter describes the development and use of the project's promotional and visual materials, which ensure a coherent identity across all dissemination and communication actions. It includes the CARINA logo, posters, roll-ups, templates for presentations and deliverables, as well as the leaflet and brochure created to promote the project's objectives and outcomes at events and through digital channels.

Chapter 6 – Events

This chapter presents CARINA's participation in external events and the organisation of internal workshops and training sessions. It explains how events serve as essential platforms for disseminating project results, fostering dialogue among stakeholders, and promoting knowledge

exchange. The chapter also distinguishes between external events, where CARINA is represented at conferences and exhibitions, and internal events, including Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Policy Innovation Labs, which facilitate hands-on collaboration and capacity building.

Chapter 7 – Collaboration with Other Projects

This chapter highlights CARINA's cooperation with other Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects addressing similar topics. It outlines joint dissemination actions, mutual promotion activities, and shared events that enhance visibility, strengthen networking, and maximise the collective impact of EU-funded initiatives working towards sustainable and circular bioeconomy solutions.

Chapter 8 – Timeline and Implementation Plan

This chapter provides an overview of the timeline and implementation of dissemination and communication activities throughout the project's lifetime. It presents the four main phases of implementation — initiation, visibility and engagement, dissemination of results, and consolidation — and links them to the corresponding project milestones. The chapter also includes the main Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to monitor and evaluate progress and impact.

Chapter 9 – Monitoring, Evaluating and Reporting

This chapter describes the framework for continuous monitoring, evaluation, and reporting of dissemination and communication actions. It details the mechanisms used to assess effectiveness, such as quantitative and qualitative indicators, and introduces the dedicated tracking tools (event tracker, training tracker, C&D tracker, post tracker). This ensures transparency, accountability, and evidence-based improvement of all dissemination and communication activities.

Part II – Exploitation IPR Management and Sustainability (Chapter 10)

This part focuses on the exploitation of CARINA's results and intellectual property, ensuring that knowledge and innovations generated within the project are protected, valorised, and sustained beyond its duration.

- **Subchapter 10.1** provides introductory information about the context in which this part has been elaborated as well as its targets and structure.
- **Subchapter 10.2** outlines the IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of CARINA. Clarifies the key terms pertaining to IPR management of the project, defines the underlying objectives and explains the main intellectual property protection instruments to be employed.

- **Subchapter 10.3** describes the methodology to be followed in this respect. introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed in order to identify the CARINA background and foreground IP, as perceived at this stage of the project.
- **Subchapter 10.4** offers a preliminary overview of the project's assets to be co-created, as identified at this stage of the project, as well as the background and foreground IPs as perceived by all CARINA partners.
- **Subchapter 10.5** Presents the individual exploitation plans per partners.

Exploitation IPR Management and Sustainability concludes on the next steps towards the exploitation of the assets of the project as well as on dissemination and communication activities.

Finally, the **Annexes** of this DCE include the event reporting template to be used across all project engagement activities, along with a comprehensive record of communication and dissemination actions, engagement events, and publications implemented by the consortium up to Month 36.

The CARINA Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan will be updated and further elaborated on a systematic basis throughout the project. **Specifically, D6.8 - Report on Dissemination, exploitation & communication activities and D6.2 - Final Exploitation plan at Month 48.** This will include the description of project's final assets, as well as the consortium's plans regarding their IPR protection and their main exploitation routes that will facilitate their exploitation after the end of the project.

4. Dissemination and Communication Plan

The strategy

The strategy focuses on establishing and executing a realistic dissemination and communication plan in line with the progress of the project and the utilisation of appropriate tools, channels and actions to communicate with the target audiences in a defined timeline.

To achieve dissemination and communication objectives in a timely and adequate manner, CARINA consortium will follow the roadmap below:

- Planning of Activities (M1 – M6): Identify the communication and dissemination strategy and plan to ensure the best impact of project's outcomes (Task 6.1).
- Implementation Phase (M1 – M48): Produce a comprehensive set of tools (supports and channels) to diffuse key messages extracted from the project results to the identified targeted groups (Task 6.1).
- Monitoring Activities (M1 – M48): Carefully analyse and assess the impact and success of dissemination activities against pre-established key performance indicators (KPIs).
- Sustainability (M1 – M48): Identify and establish mechanisms needed to ensure persistent and long-lasting visibility of CARINA outcomes (Task 6.3 and Task 6.4).
- Knowledge transfer (M7 – M48): Ensuring that elements of excellence of the project can be re-used and replicated in other projects (Task 6.2)

Target audience and dissemination and communication objectives

The general objectives of the communication and dissemination common to all project target groups including the broad public are:

- creating awareness, making the project, its vision and activities known among its targets groups;
- disseminating the achievements of the project; and
- demonstrating the benefits and impact of CARINA solutions to foster the sustainable diversification of EU farming system

The key stakeholders of CARINA with more specific dissemination and communication objectives to be passed can be segmented in the target groups outlined by the following table.

Target groups	Dissemination objectives	Communication objectives
<p><u>FARMERS-Primary Group</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers Cooperatives • Agonomists • Farmers Unions • Farmers from areas with marginal land at high desertification and soil erosion risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote CARINA biobased products • Promote CARINA solutions • Promote CARINA Stakeholder database • Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) • Promote Technical guidelines for the implementation of CARINA farming systems D1.4 • Promote CARINA Lighthouse achievements D1.2 • Promote Results from demo fields D1.3 • Promote Factsheets about local challenges and field visits D5.2 • Promote Practice Abstracts D6.4 and D6.5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA solutions • Receive feedback on public deliverables • Receive feedback on CARINA Stakeholder database
<p><u>EU BIOBASED INDUSTRY</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entities looking for affordable and sustainable domestic feedstock • Oilseed growers and crushers interested in alternative to staple oilseeds, such as rapeseed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote CARINA Stakeholder database • Expand the information about CARINA objectives through stakeholders' own networks thanks to common communication goals - raising awareness about sustainable and diversified agriculture topics • Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) • Promote Carinata and camelina seeds full characterization D2.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA biobased products • Receive feedback from stakeholders • A considerable pool of promising businesses they can tap to enhance their client portfolio • Raise awareness through CARINA activities • Receive feedback on public deliverables

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote Summary report on the main product development from CARINA D2.8 Promote Carinata and camelina seeds full characterization D2.4 Promote National roadmap and business plan reports D5.4 Promote Market opportunities for camelina and carinata in the bioeconomy D5.5 	
<p><u>BUSINESSES</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Traders Logistic operators Animal feed production plants Public and private (green banking) financial officers involved in green financing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote CARINA Stakeholder database Expand the information about CARINA objectives through stakeholders' own networks thanks to common communication goals - raising awareness about sustainable and diversified agriculture Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) Promote Social innovation solutions at local level D5.3 Promote National roadmap and business plan reports D5.4 Promote Market opportunities for camelina and carinata in the bioeconomy D5.5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA solutions Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA biobased products Receive feedback on the CARINA Stakeholder database
<p><u>POLICY</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certification entities EU Policy makers interested in understanding the best way to diversify primary production whilst promoting and sustaining biodiversity Decision-makers National and regional policy makers, interested to promote locally the adoption of conscious, sustainable farming systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote CARINA Stakeholder database Expand the information about CARINA objectives through stakeholders' own networks thanks to common communication goals - raising awareness about sustainable and diversified agriculture Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) Promote Report on integrated sustainability assessment D3.5 Promote Current policy landscapes D4.1 Promote Policy needs in the countries with demonstration fields D4.3 Promote Policy impact assessment D4.4 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA solutions Receive feedback on the CARINA Stakeholder database Receive feedback on D3.5, D4.1, D4.3 and D4.4)
<p><u>EDUCATION</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research and development institutes in sustainable farming solutions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote CARINA Stakeholder database Expand the information about CARINA objectives through stakeholders' own networks thanks to common 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate and receive feedback on CARINA solutions and biobased products Receive feedback on the CARINA Stakeholder database

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Academics and experts within the sustainable agriculture community. • Academia interested in analysing how the different policy strategies will impact in the future respect of biodiversity at national and EU level 	<p>communication goals - raising awareness about sustainable and diversified agriculture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) • Promote Technical guidelines for the implementation of CARINA farming systems D1.4 • Promote CARINA Lighthouse achievements D1.2 • Promote Results from demo fields D1.3 • Promote Factsheets about local challenges and field visits D5.2 • Promote Practice Abstracts D6.4 and D6.5 • Promote Carinata and camelina seeds full characterization D2.1 • Promote Summary report on the main product development from CARINA D2.8 • Promote Carinata and camelina seeds full characterization D2.4 • Promote National roadmap and business plan reports D5.4 • Promote Market opportunities for camelina and carinata in the bioeconomy D5.5 • Promote Report on methodological concept for all assessments D3.1 • Promote Report on economic assessment D3.2 • Promote Report on social Assessment D3.3 • Promote Report on environmental Assessment D3.4 • Promote Report on integrated sustainability assessment D3.5 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receive feedback on D3.2, D3.3, D3.4, D3.5)
<p>CIVIL SOCIETY</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Action groups such as citizen's initiatives, and NGOs, aiming to address environmental challenges with the help of sustainable agriculture. • Consumers and their associations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expand the information about CARINA objectives • Expand the CARINA mailing list (newsletter) • Promote CARINA Stakeholder database 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase public involvement and spread information about CARINA solutions and biobased products

Table 1. List of CARINA target groups with D&C objectives

Brand strategy

The visual identity of a project consists of a set of elements that forms its graphic individuality that aims to ensure consistency in the project communication and promotional material throughout its duration.

With the above-mentioned in mind, PEDAL developed a visual identity for the CARINA project:

- Deliverable, brochure and presentation's templates
- Stationery (poster and roll-up)
- Logo
- Claim

CARINA has a logo designed by the University of Bologna (UNIBO), and all of its visual materials reflect the logo's design created by PEDAL. The logo serves as a visual representation of the project's goals and values. The Brand Manual for CARINA (Annex III) contains guidelines regarding the proper usage of the logo and visual identity.

In terms of the project's claim, after analyzing various alternatives, the chosen claim is "Boosting sustainable diversification in farming systems." The final claim was chosen by the consortium from 3 options. This statement reflects the project's focus on promoting crop diversification and soil protection in agriculture. The use of the term "farming systems" indicates that the consortium has a broad and diverse representation beyond the borders of the European Union.

Tools and channels

CARINA's promotional materials

- Leaflet
- Brochure
- Poster
- Templates (e.g., for publications and presentations)
- Roll-up
- Letterhead
- Ad-hoc promotional material (tailored to the project's activities and needs – if needed)

CARINA's graphical identity

- Project logo
- Project's visual and graphical identity

CARINA's online presence

- Website
- Newsletter
- Facebook page
- LinkedIn page
- LinkedIn discussion group
- X (Twitter) account
- Promotional video
- YouTube channel

CARINA's publications

- Scientific publications
- Project's deliverables
- Other publications ((e.g., articles, press releases, etc.))
- Policy brief

CARINA's events

- Workshops
- Participation in external events and conferences
- Training events: Light houses, Living Labs, Policy innovation Labs
- Other publications ((e.g., articles, press releases, etc.))
- Final event
- Co-organisation and participation in events with projects that we have established synergies (e.g., webinars, workshops)

Figure 1 CARINA's Website homepage

4.1 Website

The CARINA website, was set to launch on M5 (March 2023), serves as the primary digital platform for disseminating information about the project to a wider audience. Designed to be user-friendly and engaging for stakeholders, the website will provide key information about the project's approach and objectives, as well as details about the Consortium.

The initial splash page of the CARINA website was launched in November 2022 (M1) as a landing page at the URL: <https://www.carina-project.eu/> Having a landing page at the very early stage of the project allowed the Consortium to fully leverage on social media channels and build initially community of the project.

All public deliverables, dissemination materials, and newsletters are available for free download on the website. Partners are expected to provide relevant content for the website's development, maintenance, and updates, ensuring that visitors are kept up to date on the project's actions and results.

All website contents are reviewed by PEDAL regarding SEO (Search Engine Optimisation) best practices for a better indexation and accessibility of the project. Additionally, the project uses Google Analytics as its web analytics service to track website traffic and assess useful statistics that will help to optimise the website and the communication and dissemination strategy.

Relevant statistics that will be monitored are the following:

- Number of visitors;
- Number of unique visitors;
- Page views
- Bounce rate
- Session duration
- Geography – what is the geographical distribution of the visitors (which countries);
- Source – how people find the website (from social media, direct etc.);
- Number of downloaded documents, newsletters, etc.

The **CARINA website** is a key communication tool for disseminating project results, providing up-to-date information about the project's goals, methodology, and impact. As mentioned in previous version website was launched at the start of the project. It acts as a central platform for stakeholders, researchers, and the general public to access project updates, publications, and resources. The website is regularly updated to reflect the project's ongoing progress and outcomes.

The website contains direct links to CARINA's social media accounts, which are prominently displayed to allow cross-promotion of content and increase visibility. It also enhances integration with social media.

4.1.1 Structure

The website is designed for ease of navigation, ensuring that users can quickly find relevant information about the project. Since the CARINA website has launched it has been continuously and regularly updated. New articles published couple of times per month, event announcements - that keep the community informed about the project's progress.

Figure 2 CARINA's website structure

The following sections are featured:

Homepage – The homepage introduces the CARINA project promotional video, news, contacts and partners.

Project – A section that provides detailed information about the project's vision, goals, and approach, with an emphasis on the role of sustainable agriculture and bioeconomy in addressing climate change.

Resources – This section is dedicated to sharing publicly available project materials, including deliverables, publications, factsheets, and other relevant documents. These resources are available for download and help disseminate the project's outcomes to a broader audience, including stakeholders and the general public.

News – The News section provides updates on important events and current developments related to the CARINA project. It includes announcements of new publications, progress updates from pilot sites, and other relevant project news that is important for stakeholders.

Events – This section provides an overview of events organized or participated in by the CARINA project. It includes details about conferences, workshops, and webinars that aim to share the project's results and foster collaboration between partners and other stakeholders.

Social innovation - The Social Innovation section focuses on the integration of social innovations into bioeconomy solutions. CARINA supports new approaches to governance and uses bioeconomy as a tool to enhance sustainability and inclusivity in the regions where it operates. It contains subsections as Living Labs, Lighthouses and Policy innovation labs, which are CARINA's most important dissemination activities.

Contact – This section provides contact information for the CARINA team, including a form for direct communication with the project. It also includes links to the project's social media accounts and other channels through which interested parties can obtain more information or engage with the project.

Forum – The Forum section serves as a platform for discussion and knowledge exchange among partners, experts, and the wider community. It may promote dialogue on various aspects of bioeconomy, sustainability challenges, and the solutions being proposed by the CARINA project.

Figure 3 CARINA's website statistics

4.1.2 Analytics and Monitoring

The performance of the CARINA website is continuously monitored using Google Analytics, tracking key metrics such as user engagement, traffic sources, pageviews, and downloads of project resources. These analytics allow the project team to evaluate the impact of the website, understand user behaviour, and guide future updates to maximize outreach and visibility.

Key performance indicators (KPIs) currently tracked between period from 23 July – 20 October 2025

- Unique visits to the website: 4 073 unique visitors
- Website pageviews: 12K pageviews
- Downloads of project resources: 440 files downloaded
- Newsletter sign-ups: 32
- Engagement from social media channels – Traffic driven from LinkedIn, Twitter/X, and other social platforms: 380
- Organic search 2 359, direct 2 255.

These metrics demonstrate active engagement with the website content and indicate the effectiveness of dissemination efforts. The data also informs optimization of the website structure, content, and outreach activities. In the reporting period the CARINA website recorded 4,073 unique visitors, generating over 12,000 pageviews. This indicates a solid and steadily growing interest in the project's activities, traffic analysis reveals a balanced mix of sources, with 2,359 visits from organic search and 2,255 direct visits, confirming both improved visibility in search engines and strong brand recognition. Additionally, 380 users accessed the website through social media platforms (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, and others), highlighting the effectiveness of ongoing social media outreach in driving engagement. These results demonstrate a positive trend in audience reach and engagement, validating the effectiveness of the implemented dissemination strategy and suggesting continued growth potential as new events, videos, and publications are released. In the table below we also can see how large impact has the CARINA project, even overseas.

Figure 4 CARINA's website demographic analytics

Accessibility and Compliance

The CARINA website is fully responsive and mobile-friendly, ensuring accessibility across all devices, including desktop, tablet, and mobile. It complies with GDPR regulations, including a clear Cookies Policy and Privacy Policy for transparency. User experience has been prioritized to make navigation intuitive, enabling visitors to easily access information, download resources, and engage with project content.

4.2 Newsletters

As part of the project, a bi-annual newsletter is produced and distributed to the project's community. This newsletter provides stakeholders with updates on the project's progress, an overview of the project's concept, and information about upcoming activities.

Developed and distributed using Mailchimp, the newsletter is released by the PEDAL, and all partners will be required to provide input and content as requested. Although the content of each issue will be agreed upon by the partners, in general, it will indicatively include the following topics:

- A brief overview of the CARINA project;
- An update on the progress of the project, including project meetings and important milestones;
- Recent results and ongoing activities related to the project;
- Plans and events for the future development of the project;
- A section highlighting relevant projects and initiatives in our field;
- News and updates from the industry

The individual networks of project partner as well as the stakeholders' database will be addressed by the newsletters in compliance with EU Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

Figure 5 Screenshot of CARINA's Newsletter

The newsletter is published twice a year (bi-annual), as originally planned, and currently reaches a total of 96 recipients: 64 email contacts from the Mailchimp audience and 32 subscribers who signed up directly via the website. By the October 2025 we have created and shared 5 newsletters.

4.3 Social Media Accounts (SMAs) and blogging

In order to promote the project and engage stakeholders, social media accounts have been created on Facebook, X/Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube during the first stages of the project. The overall objective of social media usage was to increase awareness about the project and engage with the target audience. Thanks to the appropriate leverage and involvement of multipliers, influencers and thematic groups, as well as a constant monitoring of the megatrends to identify the correct messages and arguments to be adopted, this activity increases the impact and effectiveness of the CARINA awareness and public engagement activities.

The different types of social networks used will be appropriate to reach specific target groups, and likewise the content disseminated will also depend on these groups. The same applies for paid campaigns (if any) launched for the promotion of specific initiatives or results, which will be tailored based on contents and the target audience and agreed in synergy with the Consortium.

To establish a firm online footprint, CARINA produces up to 3 news articles per month during the duration of project published on the website.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn was chosen as the platform to promote the project to a professional audience. The project's profile was created in M2 to present the project and provide updates on its progress which will be assessed using the metrics and insights provided by LinkedIn.

LinkedIn target audience:

- Farmers
- Companies in the field of project research
- EU policymakers
- Bioeconomy experts
- Research groups
- Individual researchers
- Universities
- International Organisations
- NGOs
- Financial Institutions
- Governmental Institutions

In the reporting period, the CARINA LinkedIn page maintained a solid growth trajectory and strong engagement. The page reached a total of 27,040 impressions and generated 1,186 reactions, 30 comments, and 2 reposts, reflecting a consistently active audience interested in project activities and results.

Figure 6 CARINA's LinkedIn Homepage

The average engagement rate stood at 13.7%, with noticeable peaks during March–May 2025, corresponding to the project's active event season (Lighthouse workshops, Agrokomplex Nitra, and EUBCE 2025). This period recorded the highest levels of interaction and visibility.

The page attracted 917 total followers, including 153 new followers gained organically over the past 12 months — no paid or sponsored campaigns were used. This steady organic growth confirms a growing awareness of CARINA's topics within the professional community.

A total of 483 page views and 246 unique visitors were recorded, with most visits coming from desktop users (157) and a smaller share from mobile devices (89). Demographic analysis shows that the audience mainly represents the farming sector (38.7%), followed by research services (11.2%), biotechnology, and renewable energy-related industries (each around 4–5%).

Overall, LinkedIn remains the most effective professional channel for CARINA's visibility and stakeholder engagement, particularly among research, agricultural, and bioeconomy actors.

Additionally, in the beginning of 2023, another peaks can be observed, which could be attributed to the introduction of the hashtag #carinaconsortium and a series of posts aiming to showcase each of the consortium partners. The contribution of the partners to this progress is noteworthy as they have also invited their connections to follow the account and reposted the account's posts, increasing the visibility of the account's content and gaining new followers.

Figure 7 CARINA's Follower metrics

LinkedIn discussion group

According to the Grant Agreement a dedicated LinkedIn Group has been established as part of CARINA's communication and engagement strategy. The group acts as an interactive forum aimed at reinforcing project visibility, promoting discussion, and building a professional community around the topics addressed by CARINA.

Objectives and purpose

- To reinforce trends and discussions emerging from CARINA's activities and from the thematic *Discussion Groups (Blogs)*.
- To facilitate knowledge exchange among project partners, researchers, farmers, policymakers, and industrial stakeholders.
- To create a professional network that supports the dissemination of project results and the adoption of innovative practices in sustainable agriculture and bioeconomy.
- To extend engagement beyond the project website and official LinkedIn page, ensuring continuous interaction throughout the project lifecycle.

The LinkedIn Group complements CARINA's main communication channels by enabling two-way dialogue and stakeholder participation. It provides a space for sharing updates, discussing challenges, and highlighting lessons learned from Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Policy Innovation Labs.

The activity supports WP6 objectives related to visibility, stakeholder engagement, and knowledge transfer.

A rotational coordination system has been introduced among partners, based on a shared internal table that designates, on a monthly cycle, which partner is responsible for initiating and moderating discussions within the group. This approach ensures continuity, balanced participation, and diverse perspectives from across the consortium.

Figure 8 CARINA's LinkedIn group

Facebook

The CARINA Facebook page, established in M2, utilised to promote the project's progress and share news about relevant topics within sustainable agriculture. Posts include both text and graphic content, followers are invited to events organised by the project. To monitor the performance of the CARINA page, Facebook Analytics are used. Overall, the page serves as:

- A hub for news and discussion of issues related to bioeconomy and sustainable agriculture;
- A platform for sharing updates on the project's developments and achievements (e.g., published reports, scientific publications, key events, activities, important achievements);
- A connection to other relevant groups and pages.
- Content with relevant topics

In the reporting period, the CARINA Facebook page achieved a strong level of visibility and engagement, generating a total of 1,484 interactions. Most interactions came from reactions (94.4%), followed by shares (5.1%) and comments (0.5%), confirming that visual and positive storytelling posts continue to resonate with the audience. Photo-based content remained the dominant driver of engagement, accounting for 46.8% of all interactions, while other post formats such as multi-photo or link-based content contributed around 41%. Interaction analysis also shows that 81.7% of engagements originated from followers, with 18.3% from non-followers, highlighting both strong community retention and continued outreach to new audiences.

Figure 9 CARINA's Facebook Demographic metrics

Among the most successful posts were visual summaries from CARINA's key events:

- “Looking back at EUBCE 2025” – 699 views, 367 viewers, 10 interactions
- “Discovering Camelina & Carinata at Alma Mater Studiorum” – 431 views, 294 viewers, 14 interactions
- “The Future of Agriculture within Reach: Agrokomplex Nitra” – 392 views, 228 viewers, 12 interactions
- “From EU Green Deal to the Fields” – 204 views, 125 viewers, 14 interactions

These figures confirm that photo-driven, event-focused communication generates the highest visibility and audience engagement. Posts highlighting tangible project activities, such as Lighthouses, workshops, and participation in major European events, proved particularly effective in increasing both reach and interaction quality. At this point CARINA's FB page has 132 followers.

Figure 10 CARINA's Facebook Homepage

Figure 11 CARINA's Facebook page

X/Twitter

The CARINA Twitter account, launched in M2, is a valuable tool for the project to disseminate information and engage stakeholders. By using hashtags, the project's messages can reach a wider audience, and the platform's concise format allows for effective communication with stakeholders. In addition to staying informed about industry news and the results of related projects, the Twitter account also allows CARINA to establish new partnerships and promote events. In this context, the Twitter account will:

- Disseminate the project's key messages and provide links to other project-related resources and will also keep users updated on the project's development and upcoming events;
- Collect and update news from other relevant projects, initiatives and organisations;
- Engage and create a community of followers interested in the project's topic and overall, in sustainable and diversified agriculture.

The project partners are expected to engage with the Twitter account on a regular basis by sharing its content through their personal accounts and suggesting relevant content. The account's performance will be tracked using Twitter analytics. A snapshot of the account is included below.

Figure 12 CARINA's Twitter Homepage

YouTube

YouTube account is used as an online video repository for all videos produced by the project and recorded by partners during project activities (e.g. field visits, field demonstrations etc.).

Partners select the most suitable channels operated by them to share content from the project website and social media pages such as project results, relevant insights from public deliverables, fact sheets/ brochures, possible events etc. Social media profile and cover images and banners were produced by PEDAL accordingly to fit the project's graphical identity.

PEDAL is responsible for the management of CARINA's SMAs, while all partners contributed by:

- Becoming a follower (like or follow the page/profile);
- Promoting the accounts in their networks;
- Suggesting relevant profiles that CARINA should connect with;
- Sharing interesting articles and news;
- Promoting posts and news through the SMAs of their own organizations.

4.4 Press releases

Press releases with news and info about the project activities, events and outputs are sent to specific media national online and offline media outlets. Stakeholders will be informed as well. 3-4 press releases, associated with the major milestones in the project are intended to be published over the project duration.

4.5 Promotional video

The CARINA promotional video was successfully produced and released in M12 of the project, in alignment with WP6 objectives on communication and awareness raising. The video provides a visually engaging and concise introduction to the project, presenting CARINA's mission, objectives, and core values in a clear and appealing way.

The video opens with powerful imagery of agricultural landscapes and oilseed crops, symbolising the project's focus on sustainable and climate-resilient farming systems. Through dynamic visuals, captions, and narration, it highlights the potential of camelina and carinata as innovative crops that contribute to Europe's green transition, biodiversity, and circular bioeconomy. The narrative further explains how CARINA brings together farmers, researchers, industry, and policymakers to co-create solutions for future agriculture. In its final section, the video includes a call to action, inviting viewers to explore the project website, subscribe to the newsletter, and follow CARINA on social media for further updates.

Before its public launch, the promotional video was first shared internally among project partners for feedback and validation, ensuring alignment with the consortium's communication strategy and scientific accuracy. After approval, it was officially published and promoted through all communication channels – as part of a coordinated online dissemination campaign. The video can be viewed here: [CARINA Project – Promotional Video](#)

To ensure professional quality, PEDAL Consulting coordinated all stages of video development in close collaboration with project partners:

1. Conceptualisation – defining the communication objectives, creative concept, and storyline.
2. Pre-production – drafting and finalising the script, designing the technical storyboard and mood board.
3. Production – filming, sound recording, and creation of motion graphics and 2D/3D animation.
4. Post-production – editing, audio mixing, VFX, and colour correction.
5. Promotion and distribution – development of tailored multimedia outputs and coordination of the online launch campaign.

The promotional video effectively strengthens CARINA's visibility, conveying a unified visual identity and message across channels. It serves as an accessible communication tool for both expert and non-expert audiences, helping to raise awareness of CARINA's contribution to sustainable agriculture and the European Green Deal.

5. Promotional materials

At the beginning of the project, the promotional material for CARINA was developed. PEDAL was in charge of the graphic design and content, while consortium partners provided feedback throughout the process. Over the past 36 months promotional materials were made. They are easily accessible to the public through the project's website, and they are used at physical events to attract and engage relevant stakeholders, as well as to provide more information about the project's mission and objectives. Each partner is responsible for printing and using the material as required.

5.1 Project's logo

The project's logo and visual identity were developed at the start of the project. All promotional and communication materials, including leaflets, posters, templates, websites, and publications, adhere to the project's official identity. The final logo is depicted below:

Figure 13 CARINA's Logo without claim on the left and with claim on the right

The CARINA logo features a flower that represents the crops involved in the project forming the face of a woman. This feminine representation symbolizes the root of the word CARINA, accompanied by the project's short name.

In all communication materials (deliverables, presentations, etc.) produced during the project, the EU flag and funding statement must be displayed alongside the CARINA logo.

Figure 14 EU Flag and funding statement

5.2 Poster and roll-up

Leaflets, posters and roll-ups are effective tools for disseminating and communicating information about the CARINA project. The poster and roll-up were created to draw the attention of stakeholders and provide brief information about the project. These materials were already used by partners at physical events and activities and will also be available on the project's website.

The leaflet provides the reader with information about the project's content and objectives, expected outcomes, and contact information. The poster includes graphical elements to draw the attention of stakeholders and provides basic information about the project and key stakeholder groups.

Both promotional products include information about the project's partners, including contact information and websites, and acknowledge the funding provided by the Horizon Europe program.

Figure 15 CARINA poster

Figure 16 CARINA roll-up

5.3 Templates

A comprehensive set of communication and dissemination templates has been developed to ensure a consistent visual identity and a professional presentation of CARINA across all materials and channels. All templates follow the project’s graphical identity guidelines and reflect the colour palette, typography, and aesthetic characteristics of the CARINA logo.

The available templates include:

- **Presentation template** – to be used by consortium partners during conferences, workshops, and meetings, ensuring visual consistency across all events.
- **Deliverable and report template** – for official project deliverables, internal reports, and publications.
- **Letterhead** – designed for formal correspondence and official invitations to events.
- **Concept note template** – used to present information about upcoming internal and external events, supporting their promotion by the PEDAL team and other partners.

These templates contribute to maintaining a coherent and recognisable CARINA brand identity throughout the project’s communication, dissemination, and stakeholder engagement activities. They also facilitate efficient and uniform preparation of materials across the consortium.

Figure 17 CARINA Deliverables Cover Page Template

Figure 18 CARINA Presentation template-front slide

Figure 19 CARINA Presentation template- presentation slide

Title of the workshop/event
Date/time/place
On-line/in person/

Context	Provide a short description of the background and purpose of the event, and its relevance to the CARINA project.
Target participants	Indicate the main stakeholder groups expected to attend.
Objectives	State the primary goals and aims of the event.

The Carina project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101011024.

Expected outcomes	Summarise the results or outputs the event should generate.
Format	Describe the planned format (e.g. presentations, discussions, workshop).
Agenda	Provide a structured timetable of sessions and activities.
Organiser	Indicate the organising partner(s) and contact person(s).
Registration/Contact/link	Provide information on how to register and obtain access to the event.

The Carina project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101011024.

Figure 20 CARINA Concept note Template

Figure 21 CARINA letterhead

5.4 Leaflet and Brochure

As part of CARINA’s promotional materials, a trifold leaflet and a brochure were prepared in both digital and printed formats. These materials were designed to support partner organisations in their dissemination and communication activities at physical events, workshops, and conferences, as well as to be made available for download on the project website.

Both items serve as essential tools to raise awareness among stakeholders, providing a clear and visually appealing introduction to the project's objectives, scope, and expected impacts. They highlight CARINA's mission to promote sustainable diversification in EU farming through the introduction of the oilseed crops camelina and carinata, while reinforcing the link to the Horizon Europe programme and the project's contribution to the EU Green Deal goals.

The leaflet presents CARINA "in a nutshell", offering an overview of the project concept, methodology, and activities. It describes CARINA's focus on the design of sustainable farming systems, full biomass valorisation, policy co-creation, social innovation, and sustainability assessment. The leaflet also introduces the partnership, contact information, and the project's online channels (website and social media). Its bright, nature-inspired design and concise messaging make it an effective tool for attracting stakeholders' attention during events and ensuring the project's visibility.

The brochure, titled "Lighthouses for Sustainable Farming," was developed in line with Deliverable D1.1. It provides a more in-depth explanation of the CARINA Lighthouse Model, which lies at the core of the project's innovation approach. The brochure explains how Lighthouses act as regional hubs of innovation and collaboration, connecting farmers, researchers, and stakeholders to co-develop, test, and share sustainable farming solutions.

Both materials include all required acknowledgements of EU funding and provide detailed contact, website, and social media information to encourage further engagement. They ensure consistency with the project's visual identity and strengthen CARINA's recognition across stakeholder groups.

Figure 22 CARINA Brochure – Cover

CONCEPT AND METHODOLOGY

CARINA will focus on two oilseed crops (carinata and camelina) to demonstrate that increasing the diversification of cropping systems by adopting a well-thought and effective crop combination will enhance yield stability, farmers' revenue and the overall sustainability of farming systems, and, at the same time, to supplement the bioeconomy sector.

To facilitate the deployment of innovative systems, CARINA will also address certification issues of low ILUC feedstocks intended for bio-based industry.

9 Lighthouses, 5 Living Labs, and 9 Policy Innovation Labs will be established across Europe playing a leading role in the co-creation of CARINA innovation actions.

ACTIVITIES

Designing and implementing innovative and sustainable farming systems

To design and implement new site-specific primary production systems on farm-scale. The new systems will be thoroughly analysed within the lighthouses to co-create and develop innovative and sustainable technical solutions.

Co-creation of policy interventions for feedstock provision and certification in CARINA bio-based value chains

To co-create a set of policy recommendations that can maximise economic, environmental and social synergies in the provision of certified low ILUC feedstock for bio-based value chains.

Full biomass valorisation with a circular economy approach

To valorise the co-products of carinata and camelina through the extraction of molecules having different applications in the field of bioplastics, biochemicals, animal nutrition, biofuels, biostimulants and/or biopesticides.

Integrated sustainability assessment of the new bio-based CARINA systems

To carry out an integrated sustainability assessment of CARINA bio-based production systems, including the identification of sustainability indicators for the assessment of the economic, social and environmental impacts.

Communicate and deploy synergies

To ensure wide visibility of CARINA by setting up an effective communication dissemination strategy and, at the same time, pave the way for the exploitation of the CARINA results. CARINA will achieve this objective posing attention to cluster and create synergies with other EU initiatives with strong links with CARINA.

Social Innovation to scale-up CARINA solutions for bio-based agricultural production systems

To improve understanding of the co-benefits and potential risks, and to deliversolutionsfor upscaling potential bio-based agricultural production systems through a social innovation process. To achieve this objective, CARINA will establish national living labs (LLs) and organise 'co-define challenge' workshops within technical field visits, with the aim to cocreate solutions from lessons learned, and to implement them locally to deliver tailored roadmaps and business plans.

Figure 23 CARINA Leaflet inside

PARTNERS

CARINA capitalizes on a highly experienced team of 19 partners, +5 affiliated entities, from 13 EU and Associated Countries (Italy, France, Spain, Germany, Greece, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Poland, UK, Serbia, Tunisia, Morocco, Switzerland)

ABOUT

CARINA is a cross-national 4-year long Innovation Action (01/11/2022-31/10/2026), supported by the European Union within the framework of the Horizon Europe programme.

The project focuses on new sustainable and diversified farming systems including 2 new oilseed crops, carinata and camelina, able to provide multiple low ILUC feedstocks for the bio-based economy.

get in. TOUCH.

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CARINA

Boosting sustainable diversification in farming systems

CARinata and CamellINA to boost the sustainable diversification in EU farming

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101081839.

Figure 24 CARINA Leaflet outside

Tools and channels per targets

The following table showcases how each CARINA target audience is approached by type of tool/channel.

TARGET GROUP	DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS					
	Website	Newsletters	Social media/ blogging	Press releases	Events	Video
<u>FARMERS</u>	[Teal bar]					
<u>EU BIOBASED INDUSTRIE</u>	[Teal bar]		[White bar]	[Teal bar]		
<u>BUSINESSES</u>	[Teal bar]		[White bar]	[Teal bar]		[White bar]
<u>POLICY</u>	[Teal bar]					[White bar]
<u>EDUCATION AND ACADEMIA</u>	[Teal bar]		[White bar]	[Teal bar]		[White bar]
<u>CIVIL SOCIETY</u>	[Teal bar]					

Table 2. Tools and channels per target

6. Events

Participation in third-party conferences and events plays a vital role in CARINA's dissemination strategy. These events provide key opportunities to interact with stakeholders, share updates on the project's progress, and ensure that CARINA's innovations reach a broader audience. Through active participation in external events, CARINA can promote its findings, engage with farmers, researchers, policymakers, and industry professionals, and expand its network of collaborators.

Both **external events** and **internal training activities** are systematically tracked, allowing the project team to monitor and evaluate their impact on project visibility and engagement.

6.1 External Events

CARINA has participated in and organised numerous **external events**, including workshops, conferences, and other industry-specific gatherings, where the project showcased its work on sustainable agriculture, bioeconomy, and innovative cropping systems. These events serve as valuable platforms to disseminate CARINA's findings, promote sustainable farming practices, and engage with key stakeholders.

External events are crucial for:

- Raising awareness about CARINA's goals and methodologies.
- Facilitating direct engagement with stakeholders and fostering collaborations with relevant experts.

- Promoting CARINA's outputs and innovations to a wider audience, ensuring the project's visibility across Europe and beyond.
- Present the project (concept, objectives, approach, etc.);
- Promote the project's findings;
- Promote CARINA actions and events;
- Expand the project's synergies and contacts network with relevant projects and initiatives;
- Engage relevant stakeholders in project's activities;
- Promote the project's dissemination channels (website, SMAs etc.).

Below is a list of the **20 most significant external events** where CARINA was presented from the beginning of the project:

Title	Venue	Year
The International Agricultural Exhibition AGRO SHOW	Bednary, Poland	2025
CARINA Field day 2025	Cadriano, experimental farm of University of Bologna (AUB)	2025
Meca-culturales 2025	Saint Agnet, France	2025
Agrokomplex	Nitra, Slovakia	2025
Paris International Agricultural Show	Paris, France	2025
11th Carinata biomaterials summit	Canada (online)	2024
Centennial Celebration and Congress of the International Union of Soil Sciences	Florence, Italy	2024
Conference of Agronomists and Farmers of Serbia	Zlatibor, Serbia	2024
National Scientific Conference "Nauka dla Postępu Biologicznego"	Lublin-Urszulin, Poland	2024

Table 3. List of external events (from “external events tracker”)

These events have played a significant role in showcasing CARINA's progress and outcomes. The full list of external events, including future events, is detailed in the CARINA Event Tracker document.

In order to maintain the project's visual identity at external events, the partners should use the official promotional materials (leaflets, posters, PowerPoint templates, etc.). In case a partner intends to present CARINA at an external event, they must inform PEDAL, as Dissemination Manager, in advance in order to disseminate the information appropriately through the project's dissemination channels. After the event, the partners should complete the Event Reporting template (Annex I) and the CARINA Dissemination and Communication activity trackers (Figure 11) and inform PEDAL.

6.2 CARINA workshops & training activities

The CARINA has organised and participated in several internal events aimed at fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange among stakeholders. These activities are essential for promoting the project's innovations and best practices in agricultural environments, and they contribute to CARINA's capacity-building efforts by offering practical learning experiences. The internal events include Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Policy Innovation Labs, each playing a critical role in achieving the project's objectives.

Living Labs provide regional platforms where farmers, researchers, and policy makers collaborate to test and develop sustainable farming systems. These labs offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of different agricultural practices and help adapt innovative solutions to local conditions. By engaging stakeholders directly, Living Labs foster practical learning and the implementation of real-world solutions.

Lighthouses act as key regional hubs for innovation. These centres are designed to demonstrate and optimize sustainable agricultural practices, particularly the use of camelina and carinata. They serve as demonstration sites where various agricultural technologies and practices are tested, and the results are shared with a broader audience, helping to scale up successful solutions across different farming systems.

Policy Innovation Labs bring together policy makers, academics, and industry leaders to discuss and co-create the policies needed to support the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. These labs focus on identifying policy barriers and opportunities and developing strategies to foster the widespread implementation of CARINA's innovations in the European agricultural sector.

These internal events are tracked and evaluated through the **CARINA Training Events & Workshops Tracking List**, which helps monitor the success and impact of each activity. Table below provides few of these events organised during the periodic reporting.

Title	Venue	Year
Living lab and Kimatec's biorrefinery visit	Almería, Spain	2025
CARINA living & policy lab	Baziège, France	2025
CARINA lighthouse	Baziège, France	2025
CARINA lighthouse	Teruel, Spain	2025
CARINA lighthouse	Alcalá del Río (Sevilla)	2025
CARINA field workshop	Kozie Laski (Poland)	2025
On-farm demonstration trials: intercropping	Madrin, Spain	2024
Demo meeting/ workshop	Had Draa, Essaouira, Morocco	2024
Lighthouse & On-farm demonstration trial	Blancas (Teruel, Spain)	2025

Table 4. List of Internal events (from “training activities & workshop tracker”)

Event	WP, Task, responsible partners	Type of event	Estimated date
20 online evens	WP6, T6.2 All partners	Online workshops and webinars	M1-M48
3 Multiplication events	WP6, T6.2 All partners	Online and offline workshops	M1-M48
2 Brokerage events	WP6, T6.2 All partners	Online/Physical meetings	M1-M48
Joint meetings with relevant projects	WP6, T6.2	Online meetings	M1-M48
CARINA trainings and workshops	All partners	Physical trainings and workshops	M24-M48
Final CARINA Event	WP6, T6.1 PEDAL	Physical info day	M48

Table 5. CARINA Events (from GA)

7. Collaboration with other projects

By communicating with other projects and initiatives on similar themes at the local, national, and EU levels, the consortium can shape cooperation conditions and benefit from the experience and knowledge of these initiatives. This can lead to the strengthening of the project's impact activities through additional networking and awareness of potential joint activities and ways for mutual benefit collaborations, ultimately enhancing the common wider objectives of CARINA and similar initiatives.

Joint dissemination activities, particularly with EU-funded projects, will also be sought. These collaborations could take various forms:

- Reference of mutual projects on their respective websites;
- Support each other through social media accounts;
- Sharing news, invitations to external events, press releases, and other dissemination actions through social media communication channels;
- Attending events hosted by similar projects;
- Exploration of the possibility of co-organising an event;
- Inviting participation in events organised by the CARINA consortium.

Table below provides a basic overview of relevant key European projects and initiatives with which CARINA has established collaboration links. Throughout the project implementation, several joint activities, exchanges, and dissemination actions have been realised, leading to stronger networking and knowledge sharing across initiatives working on similar objectives. These synergies continue to evolve, supporting CARINA's visibility and contributing to the common goals of the Horizon Europe community in promoting sustainable agriculture and circular bioeconomy solutions.

Project/Initiative	Brief description	Start	Countries involved
4CE-MED Horizon 2020	The CE-MED project aims to develop innovative and resilient farming systems in the Mediterranean region that do not compete for land with the food chain. The project will follow a participatory approach to identify smallholder needs and monitor and evaluate project actions. The project involves modified conventional farming systems that incorporate camelina, an oilseed crop, as a cash cover crop to increase revenue for farmers while promoting soil and water conservation. The project fulfils the three principles of Conservation Agriculture and investigates three cropping systems that involve growing camelina as a cover crop or double crop to increase organic soil cover and diversify crop rotations.	May 2020	France, Spain, Italy, Greece, Morocco, Algeria, Tunis
UNTWIST Horizon 2020	The UNTWIST project aims to enhance the resilience and stability of crop yields under changing and challenging climatic conditions by focusing on the oilseed crop <i>camelina sativa</i> . The initiative follows a participatory and multidisciplinary approach to decipher the stress-adaptation mechanisms of camelina and to develop predictive models, robust breeding tools and agronomic management strategies that enable cultivation under conditions of drought and heat. It investigates the performance of diverse camelina genotypes across varying environments, integrates genomic, phenotypic and environmental data, and translates insights into optimized cropping systems. The project contributes to the sustainability of European agriculture and supports the transition to climate-resilient, diversified bio-based value chains.	February 2023	Spain, United Kingdom, Germany, Switzerland, Hungary, Denmark
IASIS Horizon 2024	The IASIS project aims to develop and demonstrate innovative Phyto management solutions for contaminated and saline land across Europe by using selected high-yielding non-food (industrial) crops. The initiative follows a participatory and multi-actor approach to restore degraded soils while creating biomass feedstock for value-added bio-based products. The project is structured around eight demonstration sites in six countries, where optimized crops and land-management strategies are tested, and results translated into economically viable value chains.	November 2024	Greece, Italy, Belgium, Portugal, Netherlands, Poland

Table 6. Indicative list of relevant European initiatives

Through these joint efforts, CARINA strengthens its outreach and contributes to the broader Horizon Europe objective of enhancing cooperation between projects working towards sustainable agriculture, bioeconomy, and circular innovation.

CARINA consortium has already made a collaboration agreement with **4CE-MED** project (<https://www.4cemed.eu/>) in the form of:

- Inclusion of the CARINA project in the COMMUNITY section of the 4CE-MED website;
- Presentation of CARINA project in the courses and conferences organized within the framework of 4CE-MED;

- Organisation of multilateral meetings between the projects for the presentation of results and analysis of present and future joint collaboration channels.
- Dissemination of CARINA events in the agenda section of the 4CE-MED website;
- Publication of CARINA news in the corresponding section of the 4CE-MED website;
- Possibility of making technical visits to the demonstration fields of CARINA project by 4CE-MED stakeholders.

The **UNTWIST** project (<https://untwist.eu/>) focuses on unlocking the potential of agricultural and forestry biomass for sustainable bio-based value chains. Its work aligns with CARINA's objectives in promoting circular and climate-resilient agricultural systems.

Collaboration with CARINA

PEDAL and other consortium partners have engaged in bilateral exchanges with UNTWIST, exploring opportunities for joint dissemination and stakeholder engagement. The collaboration has included:

- Networking activities and mutual promotion of project results through communication channels and social media;
- Participation in joint technical visits and thematic workshops, particularly those addressing sustainable crop management and bio-based innovation;
- Cross-referencing of project updates to promote visibility and complementarity between both initiatives.

Several joint activities have already taken place between CARINA, **4CE-MED**, and **UNTWIST** projects, including online coordination meetings focused on knowledge exchange and alignment of communication efforts. In addition, two **Lighthouse events** organised by CARINA's Spanish partner, **Camelina Company España**, served as joint demonstration and networking opportunities where the three projects presented their complementary approaches to sustainable oilseed crop cultivation and bio-based innovation. These interactions have strengthened mutual visibility, encouraged joint dissemination actions, and fostered synergies in promoting circular and climate-resilient farming systems across Europe.

Figure 25 Print screen of joint event May 2024

The IASIS (<https://www.iasis-soil.eu/>) project aims to restore contaminated and salt-affected soils across Europe by cultivating selected high-yielding, non-food industrial crops and converting their biomass into high-value bio-based products. It addresses land degradation through a cascading biorefinery approach, engages farmers from the start, and develops economically viable value chains for biomass produced on marginal land.

Collaboration with CARINA

The CARINA consortium recognises the synergy with IASIS's focus on industrial crops and circular bioeconomy solutions for marginal soils. While specific joint activities are still emerging, the relationship is anchored in mutual visibility and exchange of project outputs:

- Inclusion of IASIS in CARINA's "Related Projects" list and reciprocal reference on communication channels.
- Sharing of project news and thematic alignment in the domain of resilient cropping systems on challenging soils, providing a basis for future co-organised workshops and joint dissemination efforts.

8. Timeline and Implementation Plan

The implementation of dissemination, communication and exploitation activities in CARINA follows four distinct phases, each reflecting the project's progressive development and its evolving focus from visibility and engagement to exploitation and legacy.

First phase – Project initiation and communication setup (M1–M6)

At the start of the project, the consortium established the overall communication and dissemination framework. This included the preparation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, definition of the target audiences and key messages, and creation of the project's visual identity. The CARINA website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter/X, YouTube) were launched within the first four months, ensuring an immediate online presence. Promotional materials such as the poster, leaflet, brochure, roll-up, and templates were developed to support project visibility.

This early phase also included the first communication outreach — publication of introductory posts, press releases, and short news articles — as well as participation of partners in initial external events to present CARINA's objectives and expected results.

Second phase – Visibility, stakeholder engagement and early field activities (M7–M24)

During this phase, dissemination and communication activities intensified. The project's online visibility was strengthened through regular website updates, social media campaigns, and the publication of the first newsletter. Consortium partners began presenting CARINA at international conferences and exhibitions, building recognition within the bioeconomy and agriculture communities. At the same time, the first Lighthouses and Living Labs were launched in 2023 across several partner countries (Spain, Italy, France, Serbia, Poland), marking a major milestone in stakeholder engagement and field validation. These on-site activities allowed partners to gather practical data, demonstrate sustainable farming practices, and engage with local farmers, agronomists, and researchers. Furthermore, synergies with relevant Horizon projects (such as 4CE-MED) were initiated, ensuring alignment of objectives and complementarity of outreach activities. This phase also saw the release of the CARINA promotional video (M12), which presented the project's objectives and invited audiences to follow its progress.

Third phase – Dissemination of results and multi-stakeholder collaboration (M25–M36)

This period focused on communicating the project's interim results and promoting knowledge exchange. By 2024, CARINA had organised a series of Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Policy Innovation Labs, which served as central platforms for collaboration and co-creation. The CARINA promotional video and updated brochure were produced and disseminated, while targeted campaigns on social media and the website showcased project milestones and success stories.

Strong collaborations with the sister projects 4CE-MED and UNTWIST were formalised through joint dissemination actions, shared technical visits, and cross-promotion on online platforms. CARINA partners also participated in numerous external conferences and workshops, ensuring that the project's messages reached both the scientific community and practitioners.

During this phase, CARINA significantly increased its audience reach, establishing itself as a visible and trusted actor within the European bioeconomy landscape.

Fourth phase – Consolidation, exploitation and legacy (M37–M48)

The final phase focuses on consolidating the results achieved throughout the project and ensuring their long-term visibility and exploitation. Activities in this period include the update of the Dissemination and Communication Plan, the publication of the final newsletter, and the release of the final video, which will highlight the main project achievements and their contribution to sustainable and climate-resilient agriculture.

The consortium continues to maintain active communication through the project's website and social media channels, ensuring that CARINA's results remain accessible and visible to a wide audience.

This phase also includes the organisation of the Final CARINA Event (M48), which will present the project's overall outcomes, lessons learned from Living Labs, Lighthouses, and Policy Innovation Labs, and key recommendations for practitioners, policy makers, and industry stakeholders.

Finally, the final reporting and exploitation activities will focus on securing the project's legacy by facilitating the uptake and reuse of CARINA's results beyond its lifetime, ensuring their long-term impact within the European bioeconomy.

Continuous usage during the entire project
Month of delivery – Estimated duration
Further usage throughout the project

D6.3 - Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan, updated version 31/10/2025

Table 7. GANTT chart of CARINA D&C activities (M1 - M36)

Activity	Project month	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	
Planning stage																																						
Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan																																						
Promotional material																																						
Logo																																						
Poster																																						
Presentations																																						
Leaflet																																						
Templates																																						
Digital Presence																																						
Website																																						
Newsletter																																						
Promotional video																																						
Social Media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube)																																						
Events																																						
Online events, workshops																																						
CARINA Trainings																																						
Brokerage events																																						
Multiplication Events																																						
Final Event																																						
External events																																						
Synergies																																						
Monitoring & Reporting																																						
D&C activities reporting																																						
Internal events reporting																																						
External events reporting																																						

Table 8 GANTT chart of CARINA D&C activities (M36 – M48)

9. Monitoring, Evaluating and Reporting

9.1 Monitoring and evaluation

A monitoring process was established at the beginning of the project to ensure the successful implementation of the Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy and the achievement of its objectives. This process enabled the consortium to identify potential gaps or challenges, specific needs of relevant stakeholders, and good practices that could be replicated across activities. Whenever necessary, the D&C Plan was updated to reflect modifications identified through the monitoring process, ensuring that dissemination and communication efforts remained effective and relevant throughout the project’s duration.

To evaluate the impact of the D&C activities, a comprehensive set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) was used. These metrics were regularly reviewed and adjusted based on the project’s progress and results, and the updates are reflected in the revised deliverable D6.3. The Dissemination Manager, with the support of all consortium partners, continuously monitored the quantitative indicators during each reporting period. In addition, qualitative feedback was systematically collected after the implementation of events using the CARINA Event Feedback Questionnaire (Annex II).

To ensure the accuracy and consistency of communication outputs, a team of Communication and Dissemination (C&D) Representatives was appointed within each partner organisation. These representatives are responsible for the reviewing process of all promotional materials, articles, posts, and other dissemination outputs, playing a crucial role in maintaining coherence, quality, and compliance with CARINA’s communication guidelines.

This approach allowed the consortium to assess the overall effectiveness of the D&C strategy, identify lessons learned, and implement necessary improvements to maximise the project's outreach and visibility.

The following indicators are tracked and evaluated throughout the project to measure progress against the D&C objectives. The key KPIs for the dissemination and communication activities are presented in the table below.

Assessed element	Metric	Target	Current status
<i>Unique visits to CARINA's website</i>	Nr of visits (total)	> 3,000	4 073
<i>Website views</i>	Nr of views (total)	>10,000	12 000
<i>Facebook posts</i>	Nr of posts (total)	Not specified	168
<i>Twitter posts</i>	Nr of posts (total)	Not specified	64
<i>LinkedIn posts</i>	Nr of posts (total)	Not specified	170
<i>LinkedIn followers</i>	Nr of respondents invited	> 500	917
<i>News article/blog post</i>	Nr. Of articles	48	64
<i>Newsletter</i>	Nr. of published Newsletters	8	5
<i>Promotional material developed during co-creation events</i>	Nr. of items developed	50	30
<i>Participation in external events/conferences</i>	Nr. of events	20	35
<i>Promotional video</i>	Nr. of video	1	1

Table 9 CARINA Key Performance Indicators

9.2 Reporting

To ensure the project's success, it is necessary to keep track of the dissemination, communication, and engagement activities carried out by all partners. Therefore, the reporting and documentation for the D&C plan is crucial. Throughout the project, all consortium partners should report their dissemination and communication activities on a monthly basis by completing the CARINA Dissemination and Communication Activity Tracker provided by PEDAL (available online in the project's repository).

CARINA upcoming training events	Internal training events and workshops	Planned events to be organized by partners
---------------------------------	--	--

Table 10 CARINA Reporting tools and frequency

To ensure a systematic and consistent collection of data related to dissemination, communication, and event activities, the CARINA consortium has used three dedicated tracking tools. These trackers were maintained and regularly updated by all partners under the coordination of the Dissemination and Communication Manager.

9.2.1 CARINA event tracker

This tracker collects detailed information about all internal and external events where the CARINA project was presented or promoted. It includes key data such as the event title, location, country, date, organiser, format (online or physical), number of participants, type of audience, and relevant links or materials. The purpose of this tracker is to monitor the project's presence at conferences, fairs, exhibitions, and networking events, as well as internal consortium meetings with dissemination value.

9.2.2 CARINA Training Events & Workshops Tracking List

This file records all training and capacity-building activities organised within the project, including Lighthouses, Living Labs, Policy Innovation Labs, field visits, and workshops. For each activity, partners reported details such as the title, date, location, leading organisation, format, number and type of participants, and a brief description of the content. The tracker allows for structured documentation of all interactive, educational, and co-creation activities implemented under Work Package 6.4.

9.2.3 CARINA C&D Tracker

This tracker consolidates all communication and dissemination actions carried out by the consortium. It includes entries related to website updates, social media posts, press releases, newsletters, videos, articles, and cross-project synergies. The file enables quantitative and qualitative monitoring of CARINA's communication outputs, ensuring alignment with the Dissemination and Communication Plan and compliance with the project's visual identity and guidelines.

9.2.4 Post & articles tracker

Internal document of C&D manager to track all the SM posts and website articles published on CARINA's social media and website created by PEDAL team.

We also set the Publications tracking list to records all scientific publications, conference papers, and other academic outputs produced by CARINA partners during the project. It serves as a central register to document and monitor the dissemination of scientific knowledge generated within the consortium.

Together, these tools provide a comprehensive monitoring framework that facilitates transparency, traceability, and accurate reporting of all communication and dissemination activities across the project. If any risks are identified that could impact communication and dissemination activities, or if issues arise during the implementation of publicity actions, each project partner should immediately contact PEDAL.

CARINA INTERNAL EVENTS & EXTERNAL EVENTS CALENDAR for 2025/2026												
Upcoming events tracker												
Name of the event	Country	City	Year of the event	Date/dates of the events	Related WP & Task	Choose (National, International, Regional, European)	Project partner who inserted the event	Short description of the event	More information (link)	Type of participation	Notes	
1	Ecomondo	Italy	Rimini	2025	6th November	WP4-Task 4.4	International	Bianca de Ulbarr (RSB)	Co-creation workshop of Policy Intervention Scenarios, Exploration, Transition Pathways. The main objective is to collaboratively develop and explore plausible policy intervention scenarios for bio-based value chains in Europe by investigating a) first order effects and value chain impacts of different intervention focusing on trade-offs, co-benefits and compensatory measures; b) stakeholders' role in the transition towards sustainable bio-based products.	https://www.ecomondo.com/it	Conference in person	Participation of RSB, UNIBO & Spanish
2	Nuevos cultivos para la bioeconomía en España	Spain	Almería	2025	18-Nov	WP5	National	Spanish Co-ops	T5.1 (3rd Spanish Living Lab) & T5.5 (biorefinery visit-Kimtec's facilities). Participation of RSB, Kimtec, CCE, NUFARMA, FAECA, FGAD, CACLM, URCAOYL, Spanish Co-ops + other national stakeholders		Other	Hybrid event

Figure 27 CARINA Print screen of Upcoming events tracker

Past events tracker																					
Basic info								Participants/Audience						CARINA related							
No.	Event's name	Organizer	Abbreviation	Date of the event	Location	Registration fees	Link on the event	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Policy makers	Farmers, landowners, cooperatives, visitors	Biobased industries	Logistic, logistic operator	Potential investors	Civil Society & NGOs	Overall No of participants	Countries addressed	Specific interventions for participation (e.g. distinct sub-events, ...)	Added by (Partner)	Related Work package	Related Task	Save the event documents, photos etc. respective folder on Sharepoint
13	Panel discussion "How to overcome a dry year - practical tips for a successful harvest"	Institute of field and vegetable crops	IFVCNS	20.05.2024	International Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad, Serbia		https://nasepa.com/srbija/novi-sad/	15	4	54						Serbia	none		WP1	T1.1	https://nasepa.com/srbija/novi-sad/
14	Centennial Celebration and Congress of the International Union of Soil Sciences	International Union of Soil Sciences	PULS	19-21.05.2024	Florence (Italy)	350 Euro	http://www.terramil.eu/2024/	1425	10						1338	International	Registration fee, abstract submission	PULS	WP1	T1.1	http://www.terramil.eu/2024/
15	National Scientific Conference "Nauka do Pasieki Biologizacji"	PULS	PULS	02.07.2024	Samolice (Poland)	free of charge		2	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	Poland	none		WP1	T1.1	https://www.puls.pl/
16	National Scientific Conference "Nauka do Pasieki Biologizacji"	PULS	PULS	21.22.05.2024	Lublin-Lincoln (Poland)			52	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Poland	none		WP1	T1.1	https://www.puls.pl/
17	Food Tech congress ASROCKOMPLEX	Institute for Food Tech	FMS	18-19.10.2024	Novi Sad, Serbia	175 Euro	https://foodtech.org.rs/	0	0	5000	5000	10000	7400	24000	11400	International	Registration fee	WP1	WP6	T6.2	https://foodtech.org.rs/
18	The open door day for Bails project	Institute of field and vegetal	IFVCNS	10.09.2025	Novi Sad, Serbia			40	3	4	8	0	0	2	65	International	none		WP6	T 6.1, T 6.2	https://www.ifvcns.com/
19	Paris International Agricultural Show	IAS Paris 2025	IAS Paris 2025	26.02.25	Paris	free of charge	https://www.iasparis.com/en/								58	subject in the frame of ACTA conference	ACTA conferences	ARVALIS/UR APOL	WP6		https://www.iasparis.com/en/
20	Meza culturalas 2025	ARVALIS & Association des cumas du bassin de l'Adour	ARVALIS / TI	10 & 11.09.25	Saint Agnet, France	free of charge	https://www.arvalis.com/fr/	0							12000			ARVALIS	WP6		https://www.arvalis.com/fr/
21	Meza culturalas 2025	ARVALIS & Association des cumas du bassin de l'Adour	ARVALIS / TI	10 & 11.09.25	Saint Agnet, France	free of charge	https://www.arvalis.com/fr/	0	1	11	2				30	Spain	none	Spanish Co-ops	WP6	T 5.1	https://www.arvalis.com/fr/
22	Villaggio Coldwell	Coldwell		13.06.2025	Udine	free of charge				200					200	Italy	none	Novasium			https://www.coldwell.com/

Figure 28 CARINA Print screen of Past events activity tracker

Event Name	Organizer / partner	Date of the event	Location	Event Type	Format of the event	Link to reporting template/on Sharepoint	Number of participants	Stakeholder group
3	Living lab and Kimtec's biorefinery visit	18.11.2025	Almería, Spain	Living Labs	In-person	https://sharepoint.com/	>20	biobased industries Potential investors Traders, animal feeding plants
4	CARINA living lab	13.03.2025	Bazèlge, France	Living&Policy Labs	In-person	Journee CARINA 2025	53	farmers, scientific community, cooperatives, industrie
5	CARINA lighthouse	13.03.2025	Bazèlge, France	Lighthouse	In-person	Journee CARINA 2025	53	farmers, scientific community, cooperatives, industrie
6	CARINA demo field day	9.5.25	Cedriano, Bologna (Italy)	Lighthouse	In-person	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/events/na-da-de-transferencia-cultivo-de-brassica-carina-na-provincia-de-teruel	30	farmers, students, researchers
7	CARINA lighthouse	14.05.2025	Teruel, Spain	Lighthouse	In-person	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/events/na-da-de-transferencia-cultivo-de-brassica-carina-na-provincia-de-teruel	20	cooperative's farmers, advisory services
8	CARINA lighthouse	6/3/2025	Alcalá del Río (Sevilla)	Lighthouse	In-person	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/events/na-da-de-transferencia-cultivo-de-brassica-carina-na-provincia-de-sevilla	16	cooperative's farmers, advisory services
9	CARINA field workshop	01.07.2025	Kozie Leski (Poland)	Workshop	In-person	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/w/1/sites/CARINAProject/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B70886498-8336-406D-A04D-00CFD006B1F%7D&id=CARINA_Event_Report_KozieLeski.doc&action=default&mobileredirect=true	11	farmers, students
10	Agro Show - agricultural	19-21.09.2025	Bednary (Poland)	Workshop	In-person	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/w/1/sites/CARINAProject/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B70886498-8336-406D-A04D-00CFD006B1F%7D&id=CARINA_Event_Report_Bednary%2019-21.09.2025.doc&action=default&mobileredirect=true		
11	CARINA lighthouse	4/11/2025	Daimiel (Ciudad Real)	Lighthouse	In-person	https://www.instagram.com/p/Dt1Tet2E77iachs?hls=1 https://www.facebook.com/share/p/DCAw8kUf...		cooperative's farmers & managers, advisory services

Figure 29 CARINA Print screen of past training activities tracker

10. Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability (updated)

IPR Management Overview

10.1 Objectives

CARINA's IPR management objectives reflect the need to protect all project's assets with a view of managing efficiently all the outcomes that will stem from the project's activities and ensuring the wider availability to all relevant stakeholders. Also to identify where relevant, the commercial rollout of CARINA's exploitable results after the project's completion. To this end, the main objectives of this part are the following:

- **Define** and **agree** on the CARINA IPR management methodology to be followed within the context of the project.
- **Identify** the assets that will emerge from the activities foreseen within the lifecycle of CARINA thus, determining an assets' portfolio from the early stages of the project.
- **Develop** a common understanding among CARINA partners, concerning terms and issues of the Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) IP and respective access rights.
- **Conceptualize** a preliminary frame of the IP protection that will be employed in each identified exploitable result of CARINA.
- **Prevent** and, if not possible to prevent in all cases, define and eventually dissolve any possible conflicts in IP within the consortium and beyond.
- **Establish** common guiding routes and actions within the consortium so as to safeguard the smooth operation of the IPR strategies to be implemented.

The Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability chapter is setting out how the following elements related to IP in CARINA are to be managed within the project's context, with a view on creating a path for post-project exploitation of the relevant assets:

- Background IP
- Foreground IP
- Exploitable Results
- Access Rights
- Protection of Results
- Dissemination

The above-mentioned key concepts are normally considered for designing the Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability Plan of Horizon Europe projects. Definitions of these concepts are provided in the definition section below and have been communicated to all CARINA partners.

CARINA's exploitation strategy aims to ensure that project results contribute to the uptake of sustainable low-ILUC oilseed crops in European agriculture, supporting the transition to a resilient, circular, and carbon-efficient bioeconomy. A final Exploitation Plan (Deliverable D6.2) will be delivered at Month 48 (M48). This document will present the long-term exploitation strategy of CARINA's results, ensuring their sustainability beyond the project duration. It will outline concrete post-project pathways for maintaining and scaling up CARINA's outputs, including business, policy, and social exploitation routes.

10.2 Definitions

10.2.1 Background IP

Background IP can be **defined as data, know-how or information – including any rights - owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the commencement of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project’s assets.**¹ The background needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the underlying results must be accessible to the other project partners **on a royalty-free basis**. Under this frame, all project partners must identify the background as pertinent for the project actions and grant access rights to this IP. The background of a project can be identified and agreed:

- (i) Within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, or
- (ii) in a separate agreement (“agreement on the background”).

In this respect, there are two main aspects to consider when dealing with the background of a project:

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the assets that each project partner provides to the consortium, and which are imperative for the successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and align with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

10.2.2 Foreground IP

Foreground refers to **the results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities**, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge.² These results comprise any tangible or intangible output of the project’s actions which can be protectable or not. In this respect, foreground IP can arise and be obtained from project partners in order to protect and exploit the underlying exploitable results of the project. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as foreground.

CARINA’s Grant Agreement establishes that results of the project are owned by the project partner who generates them.³ Given the collaborative nature of the project, some results can be jointly developed by several partners. In this case, **joint ownership can arise among the contributing partners and is subject to the agreement on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership**. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the CARINA Grant Agreement,⁴ it would be best practice for partners to establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership. Each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the joint-owned results unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement.

¹ See Article 16 of the CARINA Grant Agreement

² For a detailed definition of the Foreground see: <https://iprhelppdesk.eu/glossary/foreground>. Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

³ See article 16 of the CARINA Grant Agreement, Annex 5, p.4.

⁴ See article 14 of the CARINA Grant Agreement, Annex 5, p.4.

10.2.3 Exploitable Results

Exploitation of project’s results means the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned (e.g. in other research activities; or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process; or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities).⁵ Under this scheme, an **exploitable result** is defined as a project result (expected or achieved) that meets the following two conditions:

- Has commercial/social/academic relevance;
- Can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (e.g. product, process, service, etc.).⁶

Therefore, exploitable results can be a combination or part of a foreground result(s). Not all foreground items may meet the above conditions.⁷ Furthermore, exploitable results are not necessary market ready; they may require further R&D, engineering and validation before becoming commercially exploitable.

10.2.4 Access Rights

Access rights refer to one partner’s rights for requesting access to another project partner’s background and foreground to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. Additionally, access rights can be used as long as they are needed for exploiting the project’s results. The provisions governing access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follow specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Access rights within CARINA are presented in the table below:

Purpose of access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Royalty free • Unless otherwise agreed by participants 	Royalty free
Exploitation of Own results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject on individual agreement • Granted under fair and reasonable conditions 	

Table 11. Access Rights

10.2.5 Protection of Results

It should be noted that when considering IP protection, IP assets can be protected by several types of IPR, and therefore, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner.

⁵ European Commission, Glossary, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>, Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

⁶ A patent for licensing is also an exploitable result.

⁷ European Commission, Communication, Dissemination And Exploitation Why They All Matter And What Is The Difference?, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf, Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the frame of CARINA, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks;
- Patents;
- Utility models;
- Copyrights;
- Trade secrets;
- Confidentiality agreements.

Further details about each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

Trademarks and service marks

Trademarks

A trademark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered.⁸ Trademarks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trademark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it should inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that consumers can trust in a given enterprise, not necessarily known to them, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are confronted not only with a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend more and more to be offered on a national and international scale. There is therefore a need for signs that enable consumers to distinguish between different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc. These signs are called service marks and fulfil essentially the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs which are very similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria could be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a very short amendment to the existing trademark law or simply by providing for protection of service marks under of the provisions of the trademark law.⁹

Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) that offers a new technical solution or facilitates a new way of doing something. The patent holder has the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application.¹⁰

Patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Additionally, the patent owner may give permission

⁸ For the definition of trademark in Europe, see: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en Last Accessed: 17/10/2025.

⁹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law, and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68f.

¹⁰ Definition of patents in the European context retrieved from: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en , Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

to other parties, or permit them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally (e.g. European), and may also be used in non-patented territories (although in such case they would not enjoy the patent protection). Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that owners do not hold exclusive rights any longer. Therefore, it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others.¹¹

Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period.¹² The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals.¹³

Copyrights

Copyright (or author’s right) is the term used to describe the economic and moral rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works. It is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original.¹⁴ There is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, there are several works usually covered by copyright at an international level:¹⁵

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper articles;
- Computer programmes, databases;
- Films, musical compositions, and choreographies;
- Artistic works such as paintings, drawings, etc; and
- Advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator’s reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made “pirated” goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition. Finally, it is important to note that copyright only protects

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17.

¹² Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en . Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁴ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁵ Definition of copyrights in the European context retrieved from https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en Last accessed:17/10/2025.

the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original.¹⁶

Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information that provides a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that could be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It could include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes.¹⁷

Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely important issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up stage to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is generally a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitate the project development and ensure the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and security to an organization that is about to share or make available information to another organization by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement could be a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge.

There are specific criteria to determine a confidentiality agreement as legally enforceable:

- The information must be secret, i.e. not readily accessible to people that normally deal with this kind of information;
- It must have commercial value;
- The owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect it.

Approach

Throughout the CARINA project, key IP and exploitation and sustainability management are built on the pillars of identifying a common understanding concerning the background, foreground, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the CARINA DCE plan applies on a comprehensive framework which separates the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

1. Grant Agreement preparation stage;
2. Project implementation stage;
3. Post-project stage.

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as considered within CARINA.

¹⁶ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁷ Definition of trade secrets in the European context retrieved from https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk_en Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

Figure 30 IPR Management stages

10.2.6 Preparation stage

Both the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement constitute documents which include a description of several issues related to IPR. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues within the project partners. Thus, **any further advancements regarding IPR actions to put in place by project partners will be facilitated under the underlying provisions.**

10.2.6.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project. It is signed between the EC and the CARINA partners and represents the main contractual basis for CARINA while its main points and sections which refer to IPR are included in article 16 “Intellectual property rights (IPR) — background and results —access rights and rights of use”. Under this scheme, the management of the CARINA IP is regulated, whereas access rights and obligations related to the background are set. In addition, the Grant Agreement defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project’s generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination outcomes. Lastly, the CARINA GA defines transferability and access rights to results.

10.2.6.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement constitutes a contract among the partners of the CARINA consortium which aims to define rights and obligations during the partnership for the purposes of carrying out the project’s foreseen actions and activities.¹⁸ The Consortium Agreement minimises the probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities during the project and defines the access rights to be granted to the partners concerning the project. In addition, it outlines rights and responsibilities among the consortium members concerning issues of the IP.

The CARINA Consortium Agreement main points and sections referring to IPR are included in:

- **Section 8 “Results”**, that sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination.

¹⁸ See IPR helpdesk for the definition of Consortium Agreement.

- **Section 9 “Access Rights”**, which clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for the exploitation and dissemination purposes.
- **Attachment 1 “Background included”** that presents the initial list of usable background.

10.2.7 Implementation Stage

During the implementation stage of CARINA, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the CARINA partners to organise the results/assets management of the project. As the project continues, the focus will be on foreground identification, assets’ ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as on the exploitation and commercialisation of the project’s results. The CARINA IPR management emphasises on establishing robust handling procedures of the IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project in order to facilitate the exploitation of its results.

Therefore, **partners should focus on two different points:**

- Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.
- Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate and exploit the project’s assets.

In this respect, key IP related issues in the CARINA implementation phase include:

10.2.7.1 Background Identification

During the first stages of CARINA is vital to identify the relevant knowledge, know-how and partners’ data, that constitute the background of the project. Under this framework, the underlying background could be attached to the generated assets of the project, which, eventually, will help the determination of access rights, ownership issues and IPR.

10.2.7.2 Foreground Identification

A core process of the CARINA IP management is the project assets’ identification to create a concrete mapping of the projects’ assets and enhance the CARINA IP portfolio. Therefore, all IP valuable assets within the project must be identified, listed, named, described and analysed in a systematic way.

10.2.7.3 Results’ ownership

Partners have been asked (through the CARINA IPR Matrix) to elaborate further on the provisions of the Consortium Agreement regarding the results’ ownership. Special attention is paid on **handling joint ownership issues**.

10.2.7.4 Protection of results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and assets developed under the frame of CARINA depends on the protection of the project’s results. In particular, the project’s results must adequately be protected if:¹⁹

- The project’s results can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and;
- Protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

¹⁹ See: <https://cms.eurice.eu/storage/uploads/news/files/ip-management-in-collab-horizon-projects.pdf>, Last accessed: 17/10/2025.

On this note, **when considering IP protection, CARINA partners must consider their own interests along with the interests of the consortium.** Project partners should safeguard the identified exploitable CARINA results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer protection period within a suitable geographical territory. The geographical territory should be agreed by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory in which the identified exploitable CARINA results will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement regarding this matter.

The table that follows, illustrates an indicative list of different protection instruments. The ones most applicable to the CARINA project are marked, as considering the nature of the project, it is not expected to employ all the instruments in the list. Furthermore, additional protection instruments can be used when deemed suitable as the project activities progress.

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software ²⁰	X	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	

Table 12. Indicative list of protection instruments

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale or commercialization of IP in the form of products and services. IP utilization is vital for a prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it could contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that the IP protection of an asset is not always mandatory.

10.2.7.5 Exploitation of results

The identified exploitable results and assets of CARINA will be effectively exploited for commercial or any other relevant use as foreseen during the CARINA project. In particular, the CARINA consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in:

- i) Further research activities;
- ii) Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- iii) Creating and providing a service;

²⁰ Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk.

10.2.7.6 Dissemination of results

CARINA partners are set to select the appropriate means for the dissemination of the project's results (e.g. scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, open access, etc.), based on the conditions set forth in the CA²¹ and in other specific confidentiality agreements. All partners should be aware that they should first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of the underlying result.

10.2.8 Post project Stage

At the project's formal conclusion in M48, the D6.2 CARINA Final Exploitation Plan will be submitted. It will include the final outline of the use which the CARINA consortium intends to make its exploitable foreground (including its final description and sector of application) and the related plans and time frame for their exploitation.

D6.2 will describe further the activities that will be developed to deploy the dissemination and exploitation of the project's achievements and the activities that aim to ensure the sustainability of the project's results. Additionally, D6.2 will include the final findings regarding IP issues and the final update of the IPR Matrix presenting in detail the applied and registered intellectual property rights.

The aforementioned deliverable will present the final advanced strategy for the exploitation and management of IPR and the sustainability after the project ends, including also the concrete chosen commercialisation streams.

10.2.9 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The Exploitation Manager (EM) is responsible for defining the CARINA's Exploitation Plan. The tasks include preparing the respective reports and ensuring that innovative ideas which come up during the project will be thoroughly examined and assessed for potential exploitation, while at the same time all project's BG and FG IPs are properly managed. To this end, the Exploitation Manager (PEDAL) is in close communication with the Project Coordinator (UNIBO) and the Steering Committee to ensure the optimal management of all IP assets.

The Exploitation Manager and the Project Coordinator are responsible for the organization and management issues of CARINA's IPR strategy implementation. With that said, it is considered as a good practice for a partner to inform and consult the Exploitation Manager and the Project Coordinator accordingly before deciding whether to protect the results stemming from its underlying activities or not – particularly if the partner is considering a potential joint IP scheme.

Lastly, the Exploitation Manager has also a mediation role in case of IP conflicts (see Section 5.2.6), monitors project activities and feeds the development of the subsequent versions of this report in the context of CARINA.

10.2.10 Knowledge Management of the project

The management of the IP constitutes an integral part of the overall CARINA project management structure and thus it is important to establish a permanent IP monitoring during the project. In this

²¹ See Section 8.4 of the CARINA Consortium Agreement.

respect, an efficient IPR management methodology should define, from the early stages of the project, the procedures under which newly generated/identified results will be handled during the CARINA's lifecycle.

Efficient management of IP in CARINA is achieved through adopting a process able to identify IP results as well as to determine their adequate handling and protection. In this respect, it is essential to establish mechanisms that will guarantee that IP information is reliable and timely captured. In case WP Leaders identify a new asset that will be generated under their respective WP activities, the Exploitation Manager should be informed accordingly.

The CARINA Exploitation Manager and the Project Coordinator, together with the partners producing the newly identified asset, constitute the parties that will handle the screening and the managing of any newly identified assets and their corresponding IP issues. The Exploitation Manager will direct the consortium partners to establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategy based on the nature of the newly identified asset and the purposes of the CARINA consortium.

To facilitate this process, the CARINA Exploitation plan foresees to create and update a living IPR Matrix to be revised and extended with new pieces of assets and project results (FG).

10.2.11 IP Conflicts (updated)

In order to proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners are well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process not only via the IPR Matrix but also through the help of the Exploitation Manager. In this respect, project partners are asked to identify their IPR assets, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to CARINA's exploitable results according to the principal rights and obligations defined in the CA of the project.²²

The Exploitation Manager helps with the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g. on new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and to exploitation claims?

In case of IP conflict, the Exploitation Manager will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and pro-actively find solutions and sign written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, an internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of the CARINA's CA. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, a further mediation process in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules will be applied.²³ No IP conflict has been detected at this stage of the project.

²² See Section 8 of the CARINA Consortium Agreement.

²³ See Section 11.8 of the CARINA Consortium Agreement.

IPR Matrix Methodology

The IPR Matrix is used in the framework of the project to define the main IPR issues related to the Exploitation and sustainability strategy. This approach will facilitate the consortium partners to identify the background, foreground, and exploitable results. In addition, the IP protection measures, and the necessary agreements are defined to ensure the successful exploitation of the project outcomes even after the completion of the project.

The IPR methodology follows four (4) interconnected steps:

1. **Identification of the Background IP** and definition of the access rights of the consortium partners
2. Preliminary **identification of the foreground IP** that will be produced in the framework of the project’s activities.
3. Initial **identification of the exploitable assets/results** that will be produced in the framework of the project and the interest for their commercialisation.
4. **Definition of the IPR protection** of the identified exploitable assets/results that can be potentially commercially exploited by the consortium partners.

At this stage of the project, the objective of the Exploitation plan of CARINA is to define the main assets on the one hand and identify, to the extent possible, the FG and BG IPs of the project along with their corresponding access rights on the other hand. During the later stages of the project’s implementation, the IPR methodology will be devised accordingly, in order to capture and integrate the evolvement of the identified results and IPR approach of the project. In particular, the identification of exploitable assets would yield the need to establish an ownership regime among project partners for each one of the exploitable results. In addition, rules and conditions to get access to exploitable results need also to be considered. Finally, validation of the IPR needs to be meticulously employed. Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarised in the following table.

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner’s Background • Contributing Partner • Short Description of BG • Type of Protection • How will it be utilised within CARINA? • Conditions to Use within CARINA • Conditions to use outside of CARINA • Interest in further exploitation through of CARINA results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FG# • Project Outcome /Achievement/Result • Related WP • Contributing Partners • Short Description of FG • Related BG# (BG owner) • Type of Protection • Conditions to Use within CARINA • Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results • Conditions to Use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ER# • Exploitable result • Main partner • Further contributing partner(s) • Related FG# • Related project task/deliverable (if applicable) • Related BG# (BG owner) • Proposition for the ER- owner • Short description of the ER • Relevance for IP Protection

Table 13. Structure of the IPR Matrix

10.2.12 Identification of Background IP

During the first stage of the IPR Matrix the Background IPs of the project were identified.

#	Relevant Background (the name of the Background)	Contributing Partner	BG Identifier	Short description of BG	Type of protection (e.g. patent, copyright, TM, Utility model)	Conditions to use within CARINA (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA...)	Conditions to use outside CARINA (E.g. Is it confidential? Can it be shared with external? Is it currently shared with external? If yes on what conditions?)	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA's results (Yes/ No)	Remarks
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Figure 31 IPR Matrix Background Template

Multiple information regarding the Background IP is recorded in the respective template. In the second column of the table a short name of the Background is given. Then, the responsible partner is mentioned, and a number is assigned related to the Work package and the number of assets. In the 5th column of the table a short more detailed description regarding the BG is offered. Furthermore, the partners define the Type of protection in terms of patents, utility models, copyrights, trade and service marks, trade secrets, creative commons licenses, confidentiality agreements, among others. In column seven (7), the partners define how this BG will be used in the framework of the project, and then in columns eight (8) and nine (9) describe the conditions under which the consortium partners and the stakeholders outside the consortium respectively can use the BG. Finally, the partners should state their interest for further exploitation of the BG in the framework of the project through the produced results.

10.2.13 Identification of Foreground IP

In the second stage of the IPR Matrix the partners have identified the Foreground that is produced during the project's activities.

WP	#	Project result (PR)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	FG number	Type of protection (e.g. patent, copyright, TM, Utility model, CC licence)	Conditions to use within CARINA (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/ No)	Conditions to use after the end of project (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA...)
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Figure 32 IPR Matrix Foreground Template

The above template is used by the consortium partners to identify the foreground IP. In the first four columns the CARINA project achievements are listed along with the respective WP. Then, the main contributing partner is mentioned. Usually, if an FG comes as a direct result of a Task, then the main partner is the Task leader. In addition, the rest of the contributing partners are also mentioned. Similarly, the contributing partners are usually the partners contributing to the Task that the FG emerges from. In the 7th column the number of the related Background IP is mentioned while in column eight (8) is given a short description of the FG. Furthermore, a Foreground number is assigned to the respective FG. Similarly, to the background identification template, the partners also define the type of protection, the conditions under which the FG can be used by the consortium partners and the interest for the commercialization through the project results. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the end of the project shall be indicated by the project partners.

10.2.14 Identification of exploitable results

In the third stage and based on the identified FG the consortium partners define the exploitable results and the IPR management procedures:

- i) Protection
- ii) Definition of access rights
- iii) Exploitation pathways

The main aim of this third stage of the IPR Matrix where the exploitable results and the main contributors will be defined will be:

- To identify IP ownership and exploitation claims, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection, in order to timely make the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g. for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

The next table is used throughout the whole duration of the project in order to deploy the third stage of the IPR Matrix and identify the exploitable results.

ER#	Exploitable Result	Short description of ER	Main partner	Contributing	Related FG	Related BG	ER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	Most promising	Intended users	Benefits
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Figure 33 IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template

In the first three columns, the number, a short name and a brief description of the exploitable results will be mentioned. In the next two columns the main responsible partner and the rest contributing partners will be listed. In column 6th and 7th, the number of the related FG and BG will be indicated. In addition, in the next column the proposed owner of the exploitable result will be defined, while in column nine (9) the relevance for IP protection will be indicated by the responsible partner. The next five (5) columns indicate the five (5) different categories of the exploitation claims.

- **M:** Making a product and selling it.
- **U:** Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - To develop something else for sale; or
 - For R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.
- **L:** Licensing the project result to third parties.
- **S:** Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.
- **O:** Others

The partner responsible for the exploitable results with the support of the contributing partners, the coordinator and the exploitation manager shall choose which exploitation claims best fit the ER. In the final column the most promising exploitation claim shall be indicated.

Overview of CARINA's assets, background and foreground IP (updated)

10.2.15 Identified Assets of CARINA

The table below presents the identified assets and their short description as were defined by the consortium partners during this stage of the project. Here the term "asset" is used interchangeably with the term "exploitation results" (ER).

No.	Asset	Description
1	CARINA Lighthouse and regional Workshops	National lighthouse and different regional workshops are organised including along with field visits in order to share results, success factors and technical constraints with the local stakeholders. From T1.1
2	Quarterly Thematic forums	These forums provide a platform to discuss threats, risks and opportunities from the introduction of new species into local farming systems. They take place online via the CARINA LinkedIn Group and take place in accordance with WP5 and WP6, they will be also used to share success stories to inspire. From T1.1
3	CARINA System Guidelines for Farmers	These are the outcomes from the on-farm demonstration trials on the different cropping systems demonstrated in T1.2-1.4
4	Carinata and Camelina seed full characterization	As an output of the seed quality assessment and processing done in T2.1 the Pooled seed samples will be analysed by PULS for basic composition (water, fat, ash, protein), fatty acid composition, carotenoids, phenolic, volatile and other bioactive compounds, and amino acids and sterol.
5	Development of new bioproducts based on camelina and carinata co-products and residues	Two new biostimulant formulations based on carinata and camelina protease hydrolysates, respectively, incorporating additional formulation components. Two new bioherbicide formulations based on camelina and carinata oils, incorporating additional formulation components and Kimitec synergists. Two new broad-spectrum insecticide-acaricide formulations based on carinata and camelina co-products and residues.
6	Development of new food supplement line	Different food supplements based on camelina cake mucilage will be developed. Camelina cake will be exploited as stabilizer agent to replace synthetic ones and fulfil European requirements towards a more sustainable food system.
7	The partner (FLANAT) will exploit these PROJECT by exploring the potential applications of camelina derived food ingredients	The potential application of camelina oil in food market will be investigate. This product will be marketed both as a functional food, rich in omega 3-fatty acids, and as food-stuffs ingredients.
8	Monomer production from Carinata oil	Validation of carinata oil as an alternative renewable feedstock for Novamont's oxidative cleavage technology to obtain key monomers (pelargonic, azelaic, and brassylic acids) for bio-polymer and bioherbicide supply chains.

9	Economic sustainability, environmental, social and Integrated sustainability assessments	Indicators on economic, environmental and social sustainability of the CARINA systems derived from WP3.
10	WP4 Co-creation activities (including assessment of current policy landscapes, Policy innovation labs, certification monitoring, reporting and verification)	These activities will foster collaboration with the lighthouses and all stakeholders from national living labs aimed at fostering co-creation and involving them in a participatory decision-making process.
11	WP5 Co-creation activities (including integrated research and innovation process within a PPP partnership, knowledge transfer activities at local level with primary producers, definition and cocreation of challenges and social innovation solutions and biobased market prospection)	These activities will raise awareness of the primary producers and other stakeholders on the derived environmental and economic benefits from diversified cropping systems including camelina and carinata and the current and potential associated risks. They will take place by way of organising of national living labs with various stakeholder groups, joint sessions organized with market national boards, field visits in each participating country, local challenge workshops.
12	Market opportunities for camelina and carinata	CARINA as good practice example of participatory innovation between agriculture, research and industry, helping farmers to maintain good crop yields through sustainable agronomic solutions to share among farmers and primary producers in whole Europe and associated countries.
13	Low ILUC certification	The project might exploit these outcomes by the way of publishing the tailored recommendations on what aspects are to be included in a certification for low ILUC feedstocks.
14	Registration of Pelargonic acid on camelina and possibly carinata	A joint field study will be conducted by NVMT on UNIBO fields to determine the efficacy, and dosage of perlargonic acid to accelerate camelina maturity. NVMT will patent these results.

Table 14. Identified Assets

10.2.16 Background IP (updated)

The project partners identified the background IP to be used to achieve the objectives of CARINA. The Background IP is presented in the table below:

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
1	Systerre – associated indicators & databases	ARVALIS	BG1	The method and software belong to Arvalis –Institut du Végétal, Terres Inovia, Institut Technique de la Betterave & ACTA –Trademark at Agence de Protection des Programmes (IDDN.FR.001.190043.R.P.2011.000.30100). Property and use are governed by a use agreement (CG177500178). Access right to Background at the discretion of the owner.	General Conditions of Use, Trademark, Use agreement	Free to use, in compliance with the General conditions of Use	It can be envisaged indeed to deposit some data output from Systerre in a trusted repository, with the owner's consent. It is not excluded that the terms of use of Systerre will be revised to address issues of commercial exploitation in the future.	To be investigated
2	Syppre – associated data	ARVALIS	BG2	The data fully belong to Arvalis – Institut du Végétal, Terres Inovia, Institut Technique de la Betterave. Access Right to	Trademark, Use Agreement	Free to use, upon approval of the owner	Get Arvalis' approval prior any	No

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				Background is only granted to the extent that it is needed for implementation of the action			use outside CARINA	
3	Arvalis's soil database	ARVALIS	BG3	The data fully belong to Arvalis – Institut du Végétal. Access Right to Background is only granted to the extent that it is needed for implementation of the action	Use Agreement	Free to use, upon approval of the owner	Get Arvalis' approval prior any use outside CARINA	No
4	Arvalis's weather database	ARVALIS	BG4	The data belong to Arvalis – Institut du Végétal and Météo France. Access Right to Background is only granted to the extent that it is needed for implementation of the action	Use Agreement	Free to use, upon approval of the owner	Get Arvalis' approval prior any use outside CARINA	No
5	Camelina sativa	CAMELINA Company	BG5	CCE's background is any data, know-how or other information as it relates to Camelina sativa including but not limited to planting seed, growing conditions, fertilization requirements, harvest requirements, transport, crushing and processing knowledge, chemistry conversion/derivative of any camelina in situ molecules or extractions, carbon accounting, soil carbon accumulation potential, economic sustainability, environmental, social and integrated sustainability related to camelina, camelina feed	Depending on the type of background, it can include trade secret or use agreement.	Restrictions/conditions as outlined per the Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). In addition to the data, know-how or other information, the materials provided for the project, camelina seeds, are protected under CPVO and the intellectual property rights belong to CCE.	Get CCEs' approval prior any use outside CARINA	To be investigated

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				registration and food protein, oils, or supplements.				
6	Camelina sativa cultivation practices	FLANAT	BG6	Background includes and is not limited to all data and knowledge relating to cultural practices applied to the cultivation of Camelina sativa in Italy such as seed density and sowing techniques; fertilization, requirements and formulation; collection techniques and technologies; seed cleaning techniques and technologies; seed storage and transportation; seed crushing and oil extraction; oil and cake conservation/preservation and conservation of the cake. The background is extended to the environmental life cycle assessment of Camelina sativa production in Northern Italy.	Trade secrets	Access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project will be granted on a royalty-free basis on signing an NDA until final publication will be released. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end immediately at the moment of decision of the Consortium Body to	FLANATs' approval prior any use outside CARINA.	YES
7	Camelina polysaccharides extraction and formulation	FLANAT	BG7	Background includes and is not limited to all data, know-how and information related to the application of camelina polysaccharides as a carrier to improve the stability and bio-accessibility of natural polyphenols to be used in cosmetics, food, feed and supplements. The background is extended to extraction,	Patent pending	access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project at WP2/task 2.4, will be granted on a royalty-free basis. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end immediately at the moment of	Get FLANATs' approval prior any use outside CARINA	YES, on further formulations

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				separation, filtration and drying techniques and methodologies.		decision of the Consortium Body to		
8	Camelina oil composition in food and dietary applications	FLANAT	BG8	Background includes and is not limited to all data, know-how and all information related to the monitoring and evaluation of the composition of camelina oil in any potential food and dietary application, before and after any transformation process, through the proprietary validated HPLC method.	USE AGREEMENT	access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project in WP5/Task5.5, will be granted on a royalty-free basis on signing an NDA until final publication will be released. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end immediately at the moment of decision of the Consortium Body to terminate the Defaulting Party's participation in the Consortium.	FLANATs' approval prior any use outside CARINA.	YES, on further applications
9	Oilseeds crushing and by-products valorisation	SAIPOL	BG9	Saipol's (and Saipol's sister companies through the Avril Group) background is any data, know-how, trade secrets or other information as it relates to oilseeds crushing and their by-products valorisation and commercialization, including but not limited to carinata and camelina crushing, solvent extraction, oil neutralization, refining, esterification, carbon accounting, economic sustainability, oilseeds protein	Know-how, trade secrets, confidentiality agreements, patents and trademarks	Restricted use: Restrictions/conditions as outlined per the Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) or any Confidentiality Agreement or licenses if appropriate.	Restricted use: Get Saipol's approval prior any use outside CARINA.	Yes

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				meal feed and food markets, feed & food formulation and product manufacturing, vegetable oil food markets, biodiesel manufacturing and markets.				
10	Biotechnological processes for secondary conversion of raw materials	KIMITEC	BG10	Background includes and is not limited to all data, know-how and all information.	Trade Secret under directive 2016/943	Access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project will be granted on a royalty-free basis on signing an NDA until final publication will be released. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end immediately at the moment of decision of the Consortium Body to terminate the Defaulting Party's participation in the Consortium.	License	Yes
11	Process for chemical characterization of active ingredients	KIMITEC	BG11	Chemical characterization will be performed at Kimitec's facilities. Chemical characterization will be adapted to the active ingredient nature (protein hydrolysate, pyroligneous acid, botanicals, etc.) an includes and is not limited to HPLC-MS, GC-MS, etc.	Trade secret	Access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project will be granted on a royalty-free basis on signing an NDA until final publication will be released. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end	License	Yes

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
						immediately at the moment of decision decision of the Consortium Body to terminate the Defaulting Party's participation in the Consortium.		
12	Process for manufacturing and formulation of bio stimulants/biopesticides prototypes	KIMITEC	BG12	Manufacturing and formulation will be adapted to the active ingredient nature (oil or water phase), including mixing, encapsulation, emulsions, concentrated suspension, etc.	Trade secret	Access rights to background, only if needed for implementing the project it will be granted on a royalty-free basis on signing an NDA until final publication will be released. However, in case of a Defaulting Party, Access Rights granted to it shall cease and its right to request Access Rights shall end immediately at the moment of decision decision of the Consortium Body to terminate the Defaulting Party's	License	Yes
13	Kimitec candidates of natural extracts with demonstrated biopesticide activity.	KIMITEC	BG13	Kimitec will provide active principles with biopesticide activity from its collection.	Trade Secret	Access to this Background is subject to legal restrictions or limits.	Can not be used outside of CARINA project.	Kimitec is interested in exploiting commercially the BG.
14	RSB standard module for Low ILUC feedstock (wp4)	RBS	BG14	It is a voluntary addition to other RSB Certification types that enables operators to make additional claims that an RSB	Use agreement.	Disclosed only by permission and after acceptance and signature of a disclaimer	Get RSB approval prior any	Yes

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				feedstock or product is at minimal risk of causing indirect land use change. The data used for the assessment will come from WP1 and WP2 trials and WP4.			use outside CARINA.	
15	GHG tool (wp3)	RBS	BG15	GHG calculator needed to perform the environmental assessment. The data used for the assessment will come from WP1 and WP2 trials	Use agreement	Disclosed only by permission and after acceptance and signature of a disclaimer.	Get RSB approval prior any use outside CARINA.	No
16	RSB Standard for advanced Products (wp3)	RBS	BG16	RSB Standard for Advanced Product. It is based in 12 Principles and Criteria that consider environmental, social and economic sustainability of the production of bio-based product. This Standard is for use by producers of non-energy products.	Use agreement	Free of charge to all beneficiaries, any use must be correctly referenced and cited	Get RSB approval prior any use outside CARINA.	No
17	Data, know-how and other information	NUSEED	BG17	Nuseed's background is any data, know-how or other information as it relates to Brassica carinata including but not limited to planting seed, growing conditions, fertilization requirements, harvest requirements, transport, crushing and processing knowledge, chemistry conversion/derivative of any carinata in situ molecules or extractions, carbon accounting,	Depending on type of background, all listed categories except copyrights and utility models, including but not limited to issued patents, patents pending, trademarks, service marks, trade secrets, confidentiality	Restrictions/conditions as outlined per the Material Transfer Agreement (MTA). Joint ownership of any results, and further restrictions as asserted by Nuseed on a case-by-case basis.	No use without additional consent or license from Nuseed.	To be determined.

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
				soil carbon accumulation potential, economic sustainability, environmental, social and integrated sustainability related to carinata, carinata feed registration and food protein, oils, or supplements.	agreements and other restrictive use agreements.			
18	Any data, know-how cadastre and other information	INRAT	BG18	INRAT's background is any data, cadastre, know-how and other information concerning trial's regions, INRAT's experimental stations, farmers' fields, climate and soil conditions	Use agreement	Free to use with owner's consent	It can be shared upon approval of INRAT	Yes
19	Stakeholder data base and fact sheets, data of value chain and business networks	DBFZ	BG19	DBFZ will collect data of market environments, stakeholder data, business networks, regulatory framework	Data protection and privacy policy	Publication only with data owners' consent, published data are anonymized	Published data will be open access, no restriction for data use and distribution if cited correctly	Yes
20	Knowledge on camelina and carinata agronomic management	UNIBO	BG20	UNIBO owns extensive background knowledge on camelina and carinata crop management and ecophysiology	Use agreement	Free to use	Published data will be open access, no restriction for data use and distribution	Yes

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Conditions to use outside CARINA	Interest in further exploitation through CARINA results
							if cited correctly	
21	Knowledge on Life Cycle Thinking (LCT) methodological framework, on the design of sustainable business plans and on systemic approaches to policy analysis	UNIBO	BG21	UNIBO owns knowledge on the design and application of LCT methodological frameworks for various value chains and products, on the definition of sustainable business plans to implement innovative solutions and on evidence-based policy analysis and design.	Use agreement	Free to use	Published data will be open access, no restriction for data use and distribution if cited correctly	Yes
22	Knowledge on best cropping practices for camelina regrouped in Terres Inovia's published "Guide de culture Cameline", and underlying data	TI	BG22	TI owns knowledge synthesized from internal and publicly available information on camelina cropping.	Copyright for the "Guide de culture" document; use agreement for underlying data	Free to use upon agreement	Published data will be open access, no restriction for data use and distribution if cited correctly	Yes
23	Knowledge on managing glucosinolates and other secondary metabolites in oilseeds processing	TI	BG23	TI owns extensive knowledge on processing and analysing gluconisolates in the crushing process of diverse oilseeds	Trade secret	Upon agreement	Through consulting agreement	Yes

Table 15. CARINA's Identified IP BG

10.2.17 Foreground IP (updated)

A preliminary identification of the Foreground IP took place during the initial stages of the project and can be found in the table below. Additional updates or modifications are expected in the Final Exploitation Plan D6.2, which will correspond to the progress of the project and the produced results and knowhow.

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Interest in Further Commercialisation of CARINA Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
1	1.1	D1.1 Description of CARINA Lighthouses	-	ARVALIS	ARVALIS, UNIBO, CEE, TI, CRES, INRAT, ICARDA, IFVNCS, NUSEED, PULS, AUP, NUSEED, NVMT, FACA, FAECA, URCACYL, UCAMAN, FCAC	None	This deliverable describes the methodology and organisation of the CARINA lighthouses in the different countries (France, Italy, Spain, Greece, Serbia, Morocco, Poland, Bulgaria and Tunisia).	FG1	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
1	1.2	D1.4 Technical guidelines for the implementation of CARINA farming systems	-	ARVALIS	ARVALIS, AUP, IFVNCS, FLANAT, TI, CRES, NUSEED, CCE, INRAT, ICARDA, PULS, NVMT	None	This deliverable puts together the success factors for the cultivation of camelina and carinata. These factors come from the analysis of demo trials and discussion in lighthouses. These recommendations are delivered in an easy-to-use way for farmers and practitioners.	FG2	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
1	1.2-1.4	D 1.3 & D1.4	Optimized agronomic management	UNIBO	-	None	These deliverables contain the main results and guidances for growing carinata and camelina to source low ILUC feedstock in	FG3	Published data protection accordi	Free to use	No	Free to use

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Interest in Further Commercialisation of CARINA Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			ment for carinata and camelina				all the countries involved in demonstration fields.		ing to the FAIR regulation			
4	4.2	D4.2 Overview and recommendations for monitoring, reporting and verification	-	RSB	DBFZ, UNIBO, Spanish Coops	None	This deliverable will contain an overview of available certification schemes for CARINA production systems. It will address requirements for carbon farming and sustainable carbon cycles and define low ILUC criteria for feedstocks based on CARINA system	FG4	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
5	5.1	D5.1. National living labs reports	-	SPAHIS Co-ops	All involved in T5.1 & T5.5	None	This deliverable contains the outcomes of the CARINA national living labs organized in France, Italy, and Spain. The deliverable contains a summary report of the main outcomes with the localization of the living labs and analysis of the results presented. This deliverable is linked to Task 5.1.	FG5	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
5	5.2	D5.2. Factsheets about local challenges and field visits	-	TI	All involved in T5.2	None	This deliverable contains the main challenges gathered from local discussion with stakeholders and the main outcomes of the organized field visit.	FG6	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Interest in Further Commercialisation of CARINA Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
5	5.3	D5.3 Social innovation solutions at local level (Challenges definition for carina value chain implementation)	-	DBFZ	All involved in T5.1 & T5.3	None	The deliverable will depict the challenges and possible solutions identified in literature and it will report the outcomes of key stakeholders' engagement at local level as well the lessons learnt and inspiring examples of social innovation identified in the interviews and workshops.	FG7	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
5	5.4	D5.4. National roadmap and business plan reports (Country-specific roadmaps and business plans for the camelina and carinata value chains)	-	UNIBO	All involved in T5.1, T5.3 & T5.4	None	The deliverable will report roadmaps for key actors to implement social innovation solutions at national level and business plans analysing the market requirements and business opportunities for target countries and engaged stakeholders.	FG8	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
5	5.5	D5.5. Market opportunities for camelina and carinata in the bioeconomy (Bio-based market information)	-	NUSEED	All involved in T5.1 & T5.5	None	This deliverable contains the main outcomes derived from the market analysis carried out within CARINA for all the biobased products derived (i.e., oil, cake, food supplements, biopesticides, etc.).	FG9	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within CARINA	Interest in Further Commercialisation of CARINA Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
		on camelina & carinata)										

Table 16. CARINA's Identified IP FG

Individual Exploitation Plans (updated)

This section summarises, in tabular format, the assets of the CARINA project that each partner is currently interested in exploiting the most, as well as how they intend to proceed to this end.

UNIBO	Results of major interest: Definition of camelina and carinata low iLUC agronomic management for Italy; suitability of camelina and carinata under marginal land; demonstration of circularity by using pelargonic acid derived from carinata oil to accelerate camelina and carinata maturity (WP1); evaluation of social and economic sustainability of selected CARINA concepts (WP3), to be exploited in science-based policy innovation (WP4) and in defining business plans for the different actors involved in the Carinata and Camelina value chains (WP5).
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Future research and innovation project proposals will be based on the results obtained from CARINA, and the lesson learnt from camelina and carinata will be applied to other cash cover crops and possibly implemented in research projects dealing with different types of farming systems, i.e. conservation agriculture, organic farming, etc.

ARVALIS	Results of major interest: System Guidelines for farmers, trials results and collaboration with farmers evaluation of social and economic sustainability of selected CARINA concepts (WP3)
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CARINA results are expected to provide guidance for farmers and agrifood value chain actors and their members in France to implement sustainable and multiperformant crop alternatives to diversify their rotations and introduce resilient crops oriented to the new bioeconomy markets. These results can be exploited notably through targeted dissemination activities or specific trainings.

CCE	Results of major interest: CARINA System Guidelines for Farmers, Innovative camelina products developed in the project, including biostimulants, bioherbicides and biopesticides or camelina cake mucilage. as well as the recommendations in the Low ILUC certification.
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Our research and innovation team will coordinate with our commercial and value chain team in order to increase the overall value generated by camelina cultivation, incorporating camelina innovative products developed within CARINA. Additionally, our agronomic team -in contact with our camelina farmers- will coordinate with our sustainability team to implement Low ILUC recommendations during the cultivation phase, in order to maximize the Green House Gas emission reduction for camelina as a fully sustainable feedstock.

DBFZ	Results of major interest:
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Results on new biomass valorisation pathways and their impacts on sustainability are interesting for the expansion of our research focus. Besides, the methodological approach for the complex assessments is of our interest, as well as learning about stakeholders and their perspectives.

FLANAT	Results of major interest: WP1: System guidelines and low iLUC agronomic management for farmers to implement Camelina cultivation in Italy, specifically as catch crop with the tomato and feeding corn stalks, for dairy farms; WP2: Camelina
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cake polysaccharide industrial extraction and development of new concept supplements.

Future research will be focused on innovative supplements and functional food development, exploiting camelina oil and cake co-products. Polysaccharide extraction will be then implemented as functional carrier to increase bio-accessibility in supplements, feed, food and nutricosmetics. Our research and innovation team will also explore the potential application of camelina derived food ingredients.

INRAT

Results of major interest: Suitability of camelina and carinata to be introduced in crops rotation systems mainly in degraded areas in Tunisia, innovative product generated from CARINA project (bioherbicides, camelina and carinata cakes, bio stimulants)

CARINA results are expected to provide alternatives to diversify crops rotations in Tunisia especially in marginal land. Additionally, camelina and carinata will be introduced as new profitable crops for oil and cake production.

PEDAL

Results of major interest: Economic sustainability, environmental, social and Integrated sustainability assessments; WP4 Co-creation activities; WP5 Co-creation activities

As an SME consultancy, we will exploit the project's results and assets by integrating the developed knowledge, methodologies, and tools into our existing advisory and innovation management services. This integration will strengthen our service portfolio, allowing us to provide enhanced strategic, innovation, and policy support to both public and private sector clients. By embedding the project's outcomes into our advisory practice, we will not only improve the quality and scope of our services but also ensure the long-term sustainability and visibility of the project's results. Furthermore, we will leverage the new partnerships, networks, and collaborations established during the project to expand our client base, enter new market segments, and reinforce our positioning as a trusted advisor in innovation-driven regional and EU policy contexts.

SAIPOL

Results of major interest: WP1 trials results and definition of agronomic management for camelina and carinata as cover crops, especially for France; WP2 biomass valorisation with a circular economy approach and especially animal feed valorization and glucosinolate detoxification & extraction; 3 evaluations of social and economic sustainability of selected carina concepts

Our innovation team will coordinate with our commercial and value chain team in order to source camelina and carinata seeds from upstream stakeholders, crush the seeds at our industrial sites and commercialise their oil and protein meals by-products. Additionally, our innovation team will evaluate the feasibility to scale-up at the industrial level the glucosinolate detoxification / extraction processes.

SPANISH Co-Op's

Results of major interest: WP1 Trials results and collaboration with farmers; WP4 Policy recommendations for the adoption of agri-food bioeconomy systems; WP5 Value chain solutions for upscaling potential bio-based agricultural production systems

CARINA results are expected to provide a roadmap for our agri-food cooperatives and their members in Spain to find sustainable crop alternatives to diversify their rotations and introduce resilient crops oriented to the new bioeconomy markets.

TI	Results of major interest:
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New knowledge on best cropping practices and on multicriteria evaluation of camelina in cropping systems will be exploited for dissemination to growers, advisors and grain collectors, through the diversity of TI communication tools. Knowledge on processing techniques in oilseeds crushing to manage and value glucosinolates will be exploited for further R&D, including on other Brassica crops.

KIMITEC	Results of major interest: Development of new biopesticides, bioherbicides and biostimulants (WP2) for camelina and carinata crops (inter-crops), as well as for the main crops of the same field (circularity).
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CARINA results are expected to contribute to the development of new bioproducts based on camelina and carinata subproducts, including oil, cake, straws, barns, etc.

Implement the knowledge generated in the course of CARINA project to apply in further research projects dealing with different types of farming systems.

RSB	Results of major interest: WP3 environmental assessment of CARINA value chain and recommendations for low ILUC feedstock standard.
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CARINA results are expected to provide insights on the development of carbon farming and sustainable carbon cycles certification procedure. It will assess the environmental sustainability of the CARINA value chain with camelina and carinata as main feedstock.

It is also expected to contribute to the implementation of a certification standard to produce low iLUC feedstock for biobased material starting from a bottom-up approach with the direct engagement of stakeholder and civil society.

IFVNCS	Results of major interest: WP1 Definition of camelina and carinata low iLUC agronomic management for Serbia, CARINA System Guidelines for Farmers; WP2 Innovative camelina ingredients developed in the project, including bio stimulants and biopesticides. WP4 Co-creation activities; WP5 Co-creation activities.
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Future research and innovation project proposals will be based on the results obtained from CARINA. The knowledge gained from CARINA project and the project results on camelina and carinata will be applied to other similar crops and possibly implemented in research projects regarding organic farming or conservation agriculture.

CARINA results are expected to provide a roadmap for our agri-food cooperatives and their members in Serbia to find sustainable crop alternatives to diversify their rotations and introduce resilient crops oriented to the new bioeconomy markets.

Table 17. Individual exploitation plans per partner

11. Conclusion and way forward

This updated Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan (DCE) provides strategic guidance for effectively promoting CARINA's results and ensuring their long-term impact. It defines the key messages, target audiences, and communication channels to be used throughout the project. Each partner is responsible for disseminating results within their own networks, while PEDAL coordinates the overall strategy and manages online tools to maximize visibility and outreach at the EU level and beyond.

The plan will remain dynamic and be regularly updated to reflect project developments, stakeholder input, and emerging opportunities. The Exploitation, IPR Management and Sustainability section outlines the project's approach to managing intellectual property, supported by a dedicated IPR Matrix under the supervision of the Exploitation Manager.

The Exploitation Manager ensures continuous monitoring of activities, identification of innovation opportunities, and resolution of potential conflicts of interest, enabling a smooth transition toward post-project exploitation. The DCE will be further refined in D6.8 – Report on Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Activities (M48) and D6.2 – Final Exploitation Plan (M48), which will detail all dissemination and communication activities, the final assets, IPR strategy, and exploitation pathways to sustain CARINA's results beyond the project lifetime.

12. Annexes

Annex I –CARINA Event Reporting template

Events -Report Template

Description of your CARINA event

CARINA representative (name and organization)	
Event venue	
Date	
Event organized in partnership with	
Key organizational contact	
Website	
Work package	WP6
Task number	T6.2

Title (original language / English)	
Sector/s	
Stakeholders attending	
Total number of participants, out of which	
Scientific community	
Policy Makers	
Farmers, landowners, cooperatives	
Civil society	
Biobased industries	

Potential investors	
Traders, animal feeding plants	
Total number of participants:	
Countries addressed/involved	
Material created for the event (link to the internal repository)	

2. Summary of the event: Please, provide a one page of qualitative data or description of the event. (Purpose, main objectives, outcomes, takeaways and any other comments, own perspective, pictures).

3. Attendance Form – please scan and insert your signed attendance form here (if it is available)

4. Feedback questionnaire (optional)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1BReQc8VNRvi4E7vRKVdIXNwMZqYIKI6a/edit>

Annex II – CARINA Event Feedback Questionnaire

Feedback Questionnaire

Name of the Event:

Venue:

Date:

Your name:

Your position:

Your organisation:

Email:

Tel. No:

Which stakeholder group do you belong to?

Tick more than one if applicable

- Civil Society industries
 Scientific community
 Policy/public sector
 Biobased industries
- Farmers, landowners investors
 Traders, animal feeding plants
 Potential investors
- Other – please specify

Instructions

Please answer all questions as fully as you can and add comments in the free space as appropriate.

Where a numerical rating is requested, please rate aspects of your experience of the CARINA event on a 1 to 5 scale as explained below:

1 = "Strongly disagree," or the lowest, most negative impression

3 = "Neither agree nor disagree," or an adequate impression

5 = "Strongly agree," or the highest, most positive impression

Choose or state N/A if the item is not appropriate for you or not applicable to the event you attended.

Section 1: Summary

	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
Overall quality of the event	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Role of CARINA facilitating team	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Value of information available/presented in plenary	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Value of discussions & interaction	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Usefulness of CARINA event for you/your organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Venue & Logistics	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

Please use this space for any further overall comments.

Section 2: What content / views did you hear / learn about at the event that contribute to the views of your organisation and you? *Contribute to all/any sections that are appropriate.*

- 2.1 Common challenges
- 2.2 Policy/public sector landscape
- 2.3 Industry
- 2.4 Research
- 2.5 Civil society
- 2.6 Potential solutions

2.7 Other

Section 3: What connections did you make at the event of interest to you/your organisation & why are they of interest?

3.1 from Industry

3.2 from Policy/public sector

3.3 from Research

3.4 from Civil Society

3.5 Other

Section 4: What follow-up are you considering / or planning after the event?

4.1 Arranging meetings (with whom/why)

4.2 Further information gathering (on what/why)

4.3 Review of your organisations content/document (what/why)

4.4 Other

Section 5: Do you have any suggestions as to how future CARINA Workshops could be more effective?

5.1 Agenda / focus?

Thank you very much indeed for taking the time to complete this feedback form. Your additional input is much appreciated.

Annex III – C&D reporting PEDAL

Title of the article	Publication date	Source
Carina Project's Kick-Off Meeting Unveils Ambitious Plan to Transform EU Farming Systems	30.11.2022	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_projects_kick-off_meeting_unveils_ambitious_plan_to_transform_eu_farming_systems/
CARINA Workshop in Paris	23.2.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina-workshop-in-paris/
CARINA project to feature at the 10th Annual Carinata Biomaterials Summit	27.2.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_to_feature_at_the_10th_annual_carinata_biomaterials_summit/
CARINA project at the Circular Bioeconomy Conference	27.2.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_at_the_circular_bioeconomy_conference/
On-farm demonstration trial of camelina in the Rammani region of Morocco	2.3.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/on_farm_demonstration_trial_of_camelina_in_the_rammani_region_of_morocco/
Winter Camelina – field workshop in Dłóń	28.4.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/winter_camelina_field_workshop_in_dlon/
The Agriculture Minister of the Kingdom of Morocco recently visited camelina trials at ICARDA and INRA Marchouch Research Station in Morocco	8.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/the_agriculture_minister_of_the_kingdom_of_morocco/
CARINA Project Makes Waves at the European Biomass Conference & Exhibition	7.6.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_makes_waves_at_the_european_biomass_conference_exhibition/
Carina Project Team from Poznań University of Life Sciences Presents Crop Varieties at Polish National Field Days	25.6.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_team_from_poznan_university_of_life_sciences/
Winter Camelina Field Workshop Highlights Benefits of Cultivating Camelina and Carinata	26.6.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/winter_camelina_field_workshop_highlights_benefits_of_cultivating_camelina_and_carinata/
ARVALIS Showcases Carina at Les Culturales Field Event	10.7.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/arvalis_showcases_carina_at_les_culturales_field_event/
Carina at the conference 'Promotion of the Andalusian bioeconomy through European projects'	15.8.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_the_conference_promotion_of_the_andalusian_bioeconomy_through_european_projects/
Camelina as an Alternative to Combat Drought and Enhance Sustainability in Agriculture	28.8.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/camelina_as_an_alternative_to_combat_drought_and_enhance_sustainability_in_agriculture/
Advancing Agricultural Policy: Insights from the 'Sharing Our Experiences' Workshop	31.8.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/advancing_agricultural_policy_insights_from_the_sharing_our_experiences_workshop/
CARINA Project Team meets at Poznan General Assembly	20.9.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_team_meets_at_poznan_general_assembly/
Shape the Future of Sustainable Farming with the CARINA Project!	27.9.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/shape_the_future_of_sustainable_farming_with_the_carina_project/
Carinata sowing in Cereales Teruel (Aragón Region, Spain)	16.10.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carinata_sowing_in_cereales_teruel_aragon_region_spain_eg/
CARINA at RESTART Project Conference	1.11.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_restart_project_conference/
CARINA Project presented at the 9th SBA Professional Conference – The Future of Slovak Biogas 2023	11.11.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_presented_at_the_9th_sba_professional_conference_-_the_future_of_slovak_biogas_2023/
CARINA Joins Forces with 4CE-MED Project in Networking Event	30.11.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_joins_forces_with_4ce-med_project_in_networking_event/

CARINA at the Circular Bioeconomy Forum	2.12.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_the_circular_bioeconomy_forum/
World Soil Day - 5th of December 2023	5.12.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/world_soil_day_5th_of_december_2023/
PULS Scientists at the "Chemistry for Agriculture" Seminar	7.12.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/puls_scientists_at_the_chemistry_for_agriculture_seminar/
CARINA Project's 2nd Newsletter	18.12.2023	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_projects_2nd_newsletter/
Poznan University of Life Sciences - Winter Update: Braving the Cold in Poland with the Carina Project	23.1.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/poznan_university_of_life_sciences_-_winter_update_braving_the_cold_in_poland_with_the_carina_project/
Centre for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving (CRES) at Agrotica 2024 with Camelina Insights	30.1.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/centre_for_renewable_energy_sources_and_saving_cres_at_agrotica_2024_with_camelina_insights/
Exploring Social Innovation: A Journey Towards a Sustainable Future	21.2.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/exploring_social_innovation_a_journey_towards_a_sustainable_future/
CARINA at University of Seville's Open Day	26.2.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_university_of_sevilles_open_day/
Bridging Agriculture and Innovation: CARINA presented at Cordoba Congress	27.2.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/bridging_agriculture_and_innovation_carina_presented_at_cordoba_congress/
Insights from the final EUBRASWILD Project meeting and Brassica Working Group Meeting	1.3.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/insights_from_the_final_eubraswild_project_meeting_and_brassica_working_group_meeting/
4CE-MED Project Released Three New Scientific Publications	4.3.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/4ce-med_project_released_three_new_scientific_publications/
CARINA's Camelina Day in Boigneville	7.3.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carinas_camelina_day_in_boigneville/
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de Andalucía Presents CARINA at Smart Agrifood Summit 2024	20.3.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/cooperativas_agro-alimentarias_de_andalucia_presents_carina_at_smart_agrifood_summit_2024/
ICARDA's CARINA Team Engages at Maghreb Oilseeds Meetings	10.4.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/icardas_carina_team_engages_at_maghreb_oilseeds_meetings/
Carina Project at Andalusian Technical Conference	17.4.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_at_andalusian_technical_conference/
Camelina Company España and Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias Castilla - La Mancha Hosted 2nd Lighthouse Event in Daimiel	25.4.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/camelina_company_espana_and_cooperativas_agro-alimentarias_castilla_-_la_mancha_hosted_2nd_lighthouse_event_in_daimiel/
CARINA Team Releases Policy Brief on Carinata and Camelina Crops	30.4.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_team_releases_policy_brief_on_carinata_and_camelina_crops/
CARINA Field Day in Serbia	5.5.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_field_day_in_serbia/
CARINA's Lighthouses: Engaging Farmers and Researchers in Sustainable Agriculture	17.5.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carinas_lighthouses_engaging_farmers_and_researchers_in_sustainable_agriculture/
Spanish Co-ops Participation in Cultiva Day 2024	21.5.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/spanish_co-ops_participation_in_cultiva_day_2024/
Spanish Co-ops Exploring carinata Cultivation	23.5.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/spanish_co-ops_exploring_carinata_cultivation/
Recap of the 4th DG GROW Workshop on Advancing Bio-based Products and Materials	24.5.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/recap_of_the_4th_dg_grow_workshop_on_advancing_bio-based_products_and_materials/
CARINA Project at International Soil Sciences Congress	3.6.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_at_international_soil_sciences_congress/

CARINA Project's 2nd General Assembly in Thessaloniki	3.7.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_projects_2nd_general_assembly_in_thessaloniki/
CARINA Demo Field Day in Italy	10.7.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_demo_field_day_in_italy/
Introducing the CARINA LinkedIn Group	13.11.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/introducing_the_carina_linkedin_group/
CARINA at the Slovak Biogas Association Conference 2024	22.11.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_the_slovak_biogas_association_conference_2024/
CARINA and LINNA®: Revolutionizing Agriculture for a Sustainable Future (video)	18.12.2024	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_and_linna_revolutionizing_agriculture_for_a_sustainable_future/
Camelina in Seville: CARINA Project Showcased at Cereal Transfer Day	10.3.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/camelina_in_seville_carina_project_showcased_at_cereal_transfer_day/
CARINA Showcased at the 9th Agri-Food Cooperatives Congress in Spain	3.4.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_showcased_at_the_9th_agri-food_cooperatives_congress_in_spain-2/
CARINA General Assembly Gathers Partners in Hammamet to Advance Sustainable Farming Innovation	14.4.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_general_assembly_gathers_partners_in_hammamet_to_advance_sustainable_farming_innovation/
Camelina in Morocco: Stakeholders Meet and Demo Event Held in Brachoua	2.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/camelina_in_morocco_stakeholders_meet_and_demo_event_held_in_brachoua/
CARINA Project Showcased at CULTIVA 2025 in Aragón, Spain	13.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_project_showcased_at_cultiva_2025_in_aragon_spain/
CARINA Lighthouse and Demo Field Day Held in Cadriano, Italy	15.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_lighthouse_and_demo_field_day_held_in_cadriano_italy/
CARINA Lighthouse Event Held in Lleida to Showcase Camelina in Double Cropping Systems	23.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_lighthouse_event_held_in_lleida_to_showcase_camelina_in_double_cropping_systems/
Sharing Knowledge Through Practice Abstracts – CARINA Joins the EU CAP Network!	30.5.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/sharing_knowledge_through_practice_abstracts_carina_joins_the_eu_cap_network/
CARINA Lighthouse Event: Field Trial Visit with Cereales Teruel Cooperative in Aragón, Spain	2.6.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_lighthouse_event_field_trial_visit_with_cereales_teruel_cooperative_in_aragon_spain/
CARINA Lighthouse, Stakeholder Meeting, and Demo Event Held in Sebt Jahjough, Morocco	3.6.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_lighthouse_stakeholder_meeting_and_demo_event_held_in_sebt_jahjough_morocco/
Camelina and carinata in sustainable cropping systems	5.6.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/camelina_and_carinata_in_sustainable_cropping_systems/
Demonstration Day on Camelina Cultivation in Torquemada, Spain	12.6.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/demonstration_day_on_camelina_cultivation_in_torquemada_spain/
CARINA Presented at the 1st Convention of Agri-food Cooperative Technicians of Andalusia	25.6.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_presented_at_the_1st_convention_of_agri-food_cooperative_technicians_of_andalusia/
CARINA at EUBCE 2025: Spotlight on Sustainable Agriculture and Bioeconomy Innovation	1.7.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/carina_at_eubce_2025_spotlight_on_sustainable_agriculture_and_bioeconomy_innovation/
Discovering Camelina & Carinata at UNIBO's Experimental Field! (video)	9.7.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/discovering_camelina_carinata_at_unibos_experimental_field_video/
Full Biomass Valorisation with a Circular Economy Approach	18.7.2025	https://www.carina-project.eu/full_biomass_valorisation_with_a_circular_economy_approach/

Annex IV – CARINA D&C reporting partners

Communication Activity Name	Date	Lead/Author partner	Add the link to the image, video uploaded in the SharePoint or any external source
Twitter post about dissemination of the start of the project	17/11/2022	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1593170900710744064?s=20
Facebook post	29/11/2022	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0zVgPrCSoBoa2vjTdXajrrpEnkEz5adQoSFRXQw9dbahkKKA4YxmuGwSxyqLnSywl
Newsletter about the dissemination of the start of the project	29/11/2022	Spanish Co-ops	https://app.getresponse.com/view.html?x=a62b&m=Bykl4y&mc=9Q&s=n51imy&u=wBwcy&z=E_lwuJtx&
Facebook post	12.5.2022	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0cgvLCWhSmxq1jgf2d9PUaDscKAjuVt34uT7zphJ1y6StiCpqcCSqnBHsxVJocKZxl
News on the website of the start of the project	12.12.2022	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/posts/en-marcha-el-proyecto-carina-para-introducir-nuevos-sistemas-agricolas-sostenibles-y-diversificados
Facebook post	1.9.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0PVPGarwkdyv3fMyLhwAQZkpAzYkteUS1mYJZpdDuV4Z5Wqc4cTSayNmg4J2QrEnel
Facebook post	1.9.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0GEP1Jp5fcPgXyoQdqu7i8NijhB8ZtpJDqNS8LLLLjmauzmSyCTR9hRa31qTfGoSl
Facebook post	1.10.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid02NXFSMU7S2EqXfNmPady4SA5GP4CgVcb8EmXVJt8DVdDNPuz9Husz9etVd2SkJbPhl
Twitter post	16/01/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1615023673546792961?s=20
Facebook post	23/01/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0McwStr8ec1qHcnMzM8Knvk6oqVQNbxjLPYUXsvGDs5qYcYKwiHGAZkuU7Ch7z5fTAI
Facebook post	23/01/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid02NgCsBKe3zFrQANmqu3QvJPNCBBE4zq8meqrndCFskXGCjRWeFHpf9DoFiqNpcJl
Facebook post	23/01/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid022sRZTTakUFh1LjF8yv6AXzDAuLmz8HSLnbNM56SFNjK7tdzs4GKjZ61H3eNFQr8l
Twitter post	14/02/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1625468131303882754?s=20

Banner on the website about Carina Project	23/02/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/projects/WxabsRNh86-carina
Twitter post	3.6.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1632817232446193664?s=20
News on the web about Camelina as an alternative to drought	7.3.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://agro-alimentarias.coop/posts/la-camelina-se-presenta-como-una-alternativa-a-la-sequia
Newsletter about the dissemination Camelina is a drought alternative	7.4.2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://app.getresponse.com/view.html?x=a62b&m=BCH4S6&mc=ln&s=BlrucGi&u=wBwcy&z=Eyfzz7M&
Facebook post	20/07/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.facebook.com/CoopsAgroES/posts/pfbid0R7QXvDUZDT9amXe2C928Bq4xDRU9TxvMSGbKHEG3pYYW4eCLUDUVimYDRuXHeqVtl
LinkedIn posts	20/07/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/coopsagroes_newsletter-coopsagroes-carinaproject-activity-7087768584914898944-vNIG
Newsletter about video CARINA	25/07/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://app.getresponse.com/view.html?x=a62b&m=BCDQhx&mc=ln&s=BlrucGi&u=wBwcy&z=Eh1oJgE&
Twitter post about meeting in Poznan (Poland)	14/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1702258260194034070?s=20
Twitter post about meeting in Poznan (Poland)	14/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1702258265256612026?s=20
Twitter post	15/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1702764489593032848?s=20
LinkedIn posts	21/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:71110516558266851328
LinkedIn posts	25/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7111989943429738496
Twitter post	25/09/2023	Spanish Co-ops	https://twitter.com/CoopsAgroES/status/1706221826454528343?s=20
LinkedIn post	1.11.2023	KIMITEC	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7018843713636343808?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Article	1.11.2023	KIMITEC	https://kimatec.com/en/a-fifth-horizon-europe-project-aims-to-develop-a-natural-alternative-to-glyphosate/

2 days with partners involved in co-designing cropping system including camelina (Camelina Company and B Carinata Nuseed) with farmers. An interactive workshop with ARVALIS team who shared a methodology which has been discussed to adapt to each country, depending on farmers habits and behaviour. Systerre tool was also presented for the integrated assessment of these new cropping systems Results will be used to adapt and improve crop rotation and management to reach sustainability and circularity criteria.	14/02 & 15/02 2023	ARVALIS	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sylvain-marsac-b4122561_project-agriculture-biofuel-activity-7032267551808086016-HhWf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
Linkedin post	17/02/2023	ARVALIS	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/sylvain-marsac-b4122561_project-agriculture-biofuel-activity-7032267551808086016-HhWf?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop*
Twitter posts	17/02/2023	ARVALIS	https://twitter.com/prochepeau/status/1626514825487478784
Conference	17/02/2023	PEDAL	https://uphub.sk/novinky/vzdelavacia-konferencia-startup-hubu
On-farm demonstration	7.11.2022	ICARDA	Submitted information for dissemination
On-farm demonstration	15-1-23	ICARDA	Will be submitted information for dissemination
On-farm demonstration	16-1-23	ICARDA	Will be submitted information for dissemination
On-farm demonstration	20-12-22	ICARDA	will be submitted information for dissemination
On-farm demonstration	22-12-22	ICARDA	will be submitted information for dissemination
Field demonstration day: Lighthouse	1.5.2023	CCE	https://twitter.com/CARINA_Project/status/1659170350779842560

Field demonstration day: Lighthouse	19/11/2023	CCE	https://www.facebook.com/126904610098836/posts/328558403266788
Field demonstration day: Lighthouse	3.11.2024	CCE	https://www.instagram.com/p/C5oSYqzNwqn/ https://x.com/CamelinaCompEsp/status/1778472818755387833 https://www.facebook.com/126904610098836/posts/407438062045488
Field demonstration day: Lighthouse	5.8.2024	CCE	-
Field demonstration day: Lighthouse	5.10.2024	CCE	-
Field workshop	6.7.2023	PULS	CARINA Event Report Lubosz-07.06.docx
Polish National Filed Days	3-6/6/2023	PULS	CARINA Event Report Sielinko (3-6june2023).docx
Exploring Italy's Bioeconomy Together	21/03/2023	NVMT	-
Lesson with students	30/03/2023	NVMT	-
Lesson with students	gio 04/05/23	NVMT	-
Trasformare i rifiuti urbani in bioprodotti	31/05/2023	NVMT	-
Semina pomodoro da industria su pacciamatura biodegradabile	21/07/2023	NVMT	-
Twitter post	20/03/2023	NVMT	https://twitter.com/Novamont/status/1637750861316124678?s=20
LinkedIn post	24/05/2023	NVMT	https://twitter.com/Novamont/status/1661401903303991296?s=20
LinkedIn post	20/03/2023	NVMT	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/novamont_carinata-camelina-europe-activity-7043516272331894784-wh63?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

LinkedIn post	24/05/2023	NVMT	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/novamont_carinata-camelina-bioeconomy-activity-7067167598932545537-Uh0p?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
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Annex V – CARINA Event tracker

No.	Event's name	Location	Link on the event	Participants/ audience
1	the final LSMP event of 4CE-MED	Cuenca, Spain	https://www.agro-alimentarias.coop/posts/el-cultivo-de-camelina-y-carinata-impulsan-la-diversificacion-sostenible-en-varias-zonas-de-Espana	40
2	Final LSMP event of 4CE-MED	CADRIANO (BOLOGNA, ITALY)	-	30
3	the SCOOP Project annual meeting during the Bioeconomy week at AUP.	Plovdiv, Bulgaria	https://www.auplovdiv.bg/images/ProgrammeBioeconomy-Week.pdf	18
4	Webinar: Creating scale for sustainable feedstock	Online	Microsoft Virtual Events Powered by Teams	33
5	oral presentation to the annual AAIC conference (Corvallis, USA)	CORVALLIS, OREGON, USA	https://aaic.org/meetings/	70
6	SIA congress (Naples, Italy)	NAPLES, ITALY	https://www.siagr.it/it/notizie-ed-eventi/eventi-sia/561-il-programma-di-sia2023.html	150
7	The TESI 2	Tunis, Tunisia	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:p:/r/sites/CARINAProject/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B296CD782-1788-438A-9790-FC2F3A9F4681%7D&file=WP6%20INRAT%20disseminations%20activities%20CARINA.pptx&action=edit&mobileredirect=true&wdsle=0	over 200
8	The third edition of JNVR	Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia	https://liveunibo.sharepoint.com/:p:/r/sites/CARINAProject/_layouts/15/Doc.aspx?sourcedoc=%7B296CD782-1788-438A-9790-FC2F3A9F4681%7D&file=WP6%20INRAT%20disseminations%20activities%20CARINA.pptx&action=edit&mobileredirect=true&wdsle=0	over 250
9	RSB Annual Conference session on Horizon projects, and we invited Camelina company as representatives of CARINA project	Online	https://rsb.org/rsb-annual-conference-2022-agenda/	428

10	Webinar: presentation of Carina projet and main results on farming practices	Online	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rB78izF0oIc	72 + 782 (replay)
11	International Agricultural Fair Agra 2024.	Plovdiv, Bulgaria	https://www.au-plovdiv.bg/%D0%BD%D0%BE%D0%B2%D0%B8%D0%BD%D0%B8/agraren-universitet-plovdiv-na-agra24	over 1000
12	Co-design of cropping system workshop	Paris	-	10
13	Conference of Agronomists and Farmers of Serbia	Zlatibor, Serbia	https://saps.nsseme.com/	456
14	Winter Camelina – field workshop	Dłoń, Poland	-	6
15	Питања животне средине, биекономија и анализа могућности за производњу здравствено безбедне хране у АП Војводини	Novi Sad, Serbia	https://www.youtube.com/live/lhTKx3w7bs4?feature=share&t=8031	18
16	Agribusiness beyond borders: New technologies in Serbian agriculture: Opportunities for cooperation between Italy and Serbia	International Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad	-	36
17	The International Agricultural Exhibition AGRO SHOW	Bednary, Poland	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en	120300
18	Потенцијал биљних уља као сировина за производњу биодизела у Републици Србији (Potential of vegetable oils as raw material for biodiesel production in the Republic of Serbia)	Niš, Serbia	https://www.ogranaknis.sanu.ac.rs/ciklus-predavanja-dobijanje-upotreba-i-ekoloski-uticaj-biodizela-kao-transportnog-goriva-prof-dr-ana-marjanovic-jeromela-prof-dr-milan-tomicpotencijal-biljnih-ulja-kao-sirovina-za-proizvodnju-bi/	15
19	11th Carinata biomaterials summit	Online (Canada)	-	70
20	Panel discussion "How to overcome a dry year - practical tips for a successful harvest"	International Agricultural Fair in Novi Sad, Serbia	https://nsseme.com/aktuelno/vesti/panel-diskusija-kako-prebroditi-susnu-godinu-prakticni-saveti-za-uspesnu-zetvu/	73
21	Centennial Celebration and Congress of the International Union of Soil Sciences	Florence (Italy)	https://centennialius2024.org/	1526

22	Field Workshop Highlignhts Sustainable Agriculture Practices	Samolęż (Poland)	-	14
23	National Scientific Conference "Nauka dla Postępu Biologicznego"	Lublin-Urszulin (Poland)	-	52
24	Food tech congress	Novi Sad, Serbia	https://foodtech.uns.ac.rs/	0
25	AGROKOMPLEX	Nitra, Slovakia	https://agrokomplex.sk/	57495
26	The open-door day for Belis project	Novi Sad, Serbia	-	65
27	Paris International Agricultural Show	Paris	https://www.salon-agriculture.com/fr-FR	16
28	Meca-culturales 2025	Saint Agnet, France	Meca-Culturales Méca-Culturales - Les Culturales	12000
29	Jornada de Transferencia Nacional del proyecto europeo CARINA 2nd Spanish Living Lab	Online (Spain)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ID4ewKAfzZU&t=1134s	20
30	Villaggio Coldiretti	Udine	-	200
31	Carina project presentation	The Merode, Brussels	-	70
32	The International Agricultural Exhibition AGRO SHOW	Bednary, Poland	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en	90300
33	The International Agricultural Exhibition AGRO SHOW	Bednary, Poland	https://www.agroshow.pl/agroshow/en	120300
34	EUBCE 2025	Valencia, Spain	https://www.eubce.com/	1200
35	EUBCE 2023	Bologna, Italy	https://www.eubce.com/	1456

Annex VI – CARINA Training activities & workshops tracking list

No.	Partner	Event Name	Date	Location	Event Type (Workshop, Webinar, etc.)	Number of participants
1	ARVALIS, TI	Lighthouse	3.12.2024	Boigneville, Essonne, France	Workshop/field visit	55
2	Spanish Co-ops / FCAC (Federació de Cooperatives Agràries de Catalunya)/NUS EED	“Cultivo de Brassica Carinata Cooperativa Cereales Teruel” / Lighthouse & On-farm demonstration trial: growing camelina and carinata in marginal land	17.05.2024	Blancas (Teruel, Spain)	Lighthouse & On-farm demonstration trial	35
3	Novamont/UNIBO	Field Demo Day CARINA	3.07.2024	Benevento, Italy	Field demo/workshop	30
4	Spanish Co-ops/FACA, FAECA, FCAC, URCACYL, CACLM Cereales Teruel S.C./ NUSEED / RSB /Kimitec / AEAC.SV	“Camelina y Carinata: Cultivos Mejorantes en Suelos Mediterráneos” / Living & Policy Labs	30.11.2023	Online	Living & Policy Labs	30
5	UNIBO	Lighthouse	5.8.2024	Cadriano, Bologna (Italy)	On-farm demonstration trials	30
6	Spanish Co-ops/FACA, FAECA, FCAC, URCACYL, CACLM Cereales Teruel S.C./ NUSEED / RSB /Kimitec / AEAC.SV	“Jornada de transferencia: Panel Nacional CARINA” / Living & Policy Labs	28.11.2024	Online	Living & Policy Labs	28
7	PULS	CARINA field workshop	21/5/2024	Lubosz (Poland)	On-farm demonstration trials	27
8	PULS	CARINA field workshop	27/5/2024	Lubosz (Poland)	On-farm demonstration trials	26
9	Spanish Co-ops	Intercultivo de guisante con camelina / On-farm demonstration trials: intercropping	29.11.2023 - 10.05.2024	IMIDRA's Public experimental farm facilities and fields at Madrid	On-farm demonstration trials	23
10	INRAT	A field visit to the experimental station of INRAT in KEF	26.04.2024	KEF, Tunisia	Field visit	20

11	ICARDA INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURE	Demo meeting	18.04.2023	Souk El Arbba, Morocco	Field demo/workshop	20
12	PULS	CARINA field workshop	23/6/2024	Dłóń (Poland)	On-farm demonstration trials	20
13	Spanish Co-ops / CACLM	La camelina en rotación en tierras marginales/ On-farm demonstration trials: growing camelina in marginal land	11.04.2024	CCE's facilities and experimental fields at Daimiel (Castilla-La-Mancha)	On-farm demonstration trials: growing camelina in marginal land	19
14	UNIBO	CARINA training event for students	21.11.2024	Bologna, Italy	Training course for students	18
15	ICARDA INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURE	Demo meeting	20.03.2023	Had Draa, Essaouira, Morocco	Field demo/workshop	17
16	ICARDA INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURE	Demo meeting	11.04.2023	Rommani, Morocco	Field demo/workshop	17
17	Spanish Co-ops / FCAC (Federació de Cooperatives Agràries de Catalunya)	La camelina en rotación de doble cultivo / On-farm demonstration trials: cash-cover cropping	08.05.2024	Agroperera – Penelles (Lleida, Spain)	On-farm demonstration trials: cash-cover cropping	16
18	ICARDA INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR AGRICULTURE	Demo meeting	23.04.2023	Souk El Arbba, Morocco	Field demo/workshop	16
19	PULS	CARINA field workshop	7.2.2024	Samolęż (Poland)	On-farm demonstration trials	13
20	ARVALIS	Lighthouse	16.05.2023	Boigneville, Essonne, France	Workshop/field visit	12
21	Spanish Co-ops /URCACYL/NUS EED	“Cultivo de Brassica Carinata en Toro” / Lighthouse	03.06.2024	Toro (Zamora, Spain)	Lighthouse	10
22	PULS	CARINA field workshop	6.7.2023	Lubosz (Poland)	On-farm demonstration trials	6
23	ARVALIS	Lighthouse	16.09.24	Baziège, Haute-Garonne, France	Workshop/field visit	5
24	INRAT	Lighthouse	28/09/2023	Hamama biyadha, seliana Tunisia	Field visit	Not directly measured
25	INRAT	Lighthouse	3.8.2024	INRAT, ARIANA, TUNIS	workshop	Not directly measured
26	CCE/SPANISH CO-OPS/CACLM	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit with farmers to a camelina harvest arranged jointly within the project 4CE-MED.	21/06/2023	Cuenca, Spain	Collaboration with EU-funded projects	15

27	CACLM	Convention of agri-food cooperative technicians	27/10/2023	Albacete, Spain	Education and Training events	100
28	CCE/SPANISH CO-OPS	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA, 4CE-MED UNTWIST and other projects as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	5.10.2024	Madrid, Spain	Education and Training events	25
29	FAECA	Promotion of the Andalusian bioeconomy through European projects	5.7.2023	Málaga, Spain	Clustering activities	30
30	FACA/SPANISH CO-OPS	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a carinata trial run by FACA to explain farmers the agronomic aspects of the crop, the project objectives, farmer experience, etc.	17/05/2024	Teruel, Spain	Education and Training events	30
31	ARVALIS/Terres Inovia	Lighthouse + Field visits together with the 4CE-MED project	3.12.2024	Boigneville (France)	Education and Training events	50
32	ARVALIS	Poster about CARINA at les Cultureles event (France)	14/06/2023	Congerville-Thionville (France)	Education and Training events	15000
33	CCE/FCAC	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA, 4CE-MED UNTWIST and other projects as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	5.11.2024	Lleida	Education and Training events	16
34	CCE/CACLM	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA, 4CE-MED UNTWIST and other projects as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	5.8.2024	Daimiel	Education and Training events	19
35	CCE/URCACYL	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA, 4CE-MED UNTWIST and other projects as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	6-Mar-2024	Villanueva del Puente	Education and Training events	10

36	UNIBO	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run and workshop to explain CARINA and the agronomic aspects of the crop	5.8.2 024	CADRIANO (BOLOGNA, ITALY)	Education and Training events	45
37	AUP	Presentation of CARINA project - lectures and field visits with farmers and students in "Plant biodiversity in agriculture" course.	1.3.2 023	Plovdiv, Bulgaria	Education and Training events	33
38	CCE/FAECA	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA project as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	6.3.2 025	Alcalá del Río (Seville, Spain)	Education and Training events	16
39	CCE/CACLM	T1.1. Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA project as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	11.4. 2025	Daimiel (Ciudad Real)	Education and Training events	60
40	CCE/URCACYL	T1.1-Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA project as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	12- May- 2025	Torquemada (Palencia)	Education and Training events	18
41	CCE/FCAC	T1.1-Lighthouse. Field visit at a camelina trial run by CCE and workshop to explain CARINA project as well as all the agronomic aspects of the crop	6.5.2 025	Menàrguens (Lleida)	Education and Training events	Not directly measured
42	Arvalis/Terres Inovia	Lighthouse + Field visit	13/03 /2025	Baziège (France)	Education and Training events	50
43	Cooperativas Agro- alimentarias de España	Camelina y Carinata: cultivos mejorantes en suelos mediterraneos (Camelina and carinata: improving crops in mediterranean soils) 1st Spanish Living Lab	30.11 .2023	Online (Spain)	Living Lab	6
44	INRAT	Lighthouse/living labs. Field visit at a camelina/carinata trials run to explain CARINA and the agronomic aspects of the crop	5.7.2 024	El Kef, Tunisia	Meetings	20

45	Demo Day Natural Power Life	Novamont	-	-	18/19.07.2025	100
46	CARINA Field day 2025	Institute of field and vegetable crops		IFVCNS	05.09.2025.	64
47	IFVCNS	CARINA Field day 2025	04.06.2025	IFVCNS	CARINA Field day 2025	19
48	IFVCNS	CARINA Training event	18.06.2025	IFVCNS	CARINA Training event	35
49	CCE, FAECA	CARINA lighthouse: TUNISIA 28 September 2023	3.6.2025	CCE, FAECA	CARINA lighthouse	16
50	CCE, CACLM	CARINA lighthouse: TUNISIA 8 March 2024	11.4.2025	CCE, CACLM	CARINA lighthouse	Not directly measured
51	CCE, FCAC	CARINA lighthouse: TUNISIA 4 June 2025	5.6.2025	CCE, FCAC	CARINA lighthouse	Not directly measured
52	UNIBO	CARINA Field day 2025	5.9.2025	UNIBO	CARINA Field day 2025	27
53	IFVCNS	CARINA Field day	25.04.2024	IFVCNS	CARINA Field day	4
54	IFVCNS	IFVCNS field day	23.05.2024	IFVCNS	IFVCNS field day	47
55	Living lab and Kimitec's biorrefinery visit	Kimitec, Spanish Co-ops, CCE, RSB, UNIBO, FAECA...	18.11.2025	Almería, Spain	Living Labs	>20
56	CARINA living lab	ARVALIS / TI / SAIPOL	13.03.2025	Baziège, France	Living&Policy Labs	53
57	CARINA lighthouse	ARVALIS / TI	13.03.2025	Baziège, France	Lighthouse	53
58	CARINA demo field day	UNIBO	9.5.25	Cadriano, Bologna (Italy)	Lighthouse	30
59	CARINA lighthouse	FACA/Cereales Teruel S.C.	14.05.2025	Teruel, Spain	Lighthouse	20
60	CARINA lighthouse	CCE, FAECA	3.6.2025	Alcalá del Río (Sevilla)	Lighthouse	16
61	CARINA field workshop	PULS	01.07.2025	Kozie Laski (Poland)	Workshop	11
62	Agro Show - agricultural exhibition	PULS	19-21.09.2025	Bednary (Poland)	Workshop	Not directly measured
63	CARINA lighthouse	CCE, CACLM	11.4.2025	Daimiel (Ciudad Real)	Lighthouse	Not directly measured
64	CARINA lighthouse	CCE, FCAC	5.6.2025	Menàrguens - Penelles	Lighthouse	Not directly measured
65	CARINA Training event	IFVCNS	18/06/2025	Rimski šančevi, Novi Sad, Serbia	Training event	Not directly measured

Annex VII – CARINA Publications tracking list

Title of the journal or equivalent	Journal number	Peer-review	Was the publication available in open access?	PID of deposited publication
<i>Book of Abstracts, 16th International Rapeseed Congress (IRC): Global Crop - Golden Opportunities, Sidney, 24-27 September 2023</i>	-	Yes	Yes	http://fiver.ifvcns.rs/handle/123456789/3752
<i>Zbornik apstrakata, 10. Simpozijum Društva selekcionera i semenara Republike Srbije i 7. Simpozijum Sekcije za oplemenjivanje organizama Društva genetičara Srbije, Vrnjačka Banja, 16-18.10.2023.</i>	978-86-87109-17-9	Yes	Yes	http://fiver.ifvcns.rs/handle/123456789/4005
<i>Zbornik izvoda, 11. Simpozijum inovacije u ratarskoj i povrtarskoj proizvodnji, Beograd, 12-13.10.2023</i>	-	Yes	Yes	http://fiver.ifvcns.rs/handle/123456789/4026
5th National Conference for students and doctoral students entitled "The natural environment as an area of research"	-	-	-	no book of abstract
8th National Conference of Doctoral Students in Life Sciences BioOpen	-	-	-	Księga Abstraktów BioOpen 13-14.04.2023.pdf
Environment-Plant-Animal-Product: 2 nd International PhD Students Conference at the University of Life Sciences in Lublin	-	-	-	ICDSUPL2-P019 – University of Life Sciences in Lublin
16th Copernican Doctoral Seminar in Toruń	-	-	-	Załączniki — OneDrive (sharepoint.com)
47th International Scientific and Technical Seminar CHEMISTRY FOR AGRICULTURE	-	-	-	47. Międzynarodowe Seminarium Naukowo-Techniczne Chemistry for Agriculture, Karpacz, 26-29 listopada 2023 (wcss.pl)
9th National Conference of Doctoral Students in Life Sciences BioOpen	-	-	-	księga abstraktów bioopen 13-14.04.2023 (lodz.pl)
Forests	ISSN: 1999-4907	Yes	https://doi.org/10.3390/f15010105	Forests Free Full-Text Diverse Approaches to Insect Control: Utilizing <i>Brassica carinata</i> (A.) Braun and <i>Camelina sativa</i> (L.) Crantz Oil as Modern Bioinsecticides (mdpi.com)
47th International Scientific and Technical Seminar	-	-	-	47. Międzynarodowe Seminarium Naukowo-Techniczne Chemistry for

CHEMISTRY FOR AGRICULTURE				Agriculture, Karpacz, 26-29 listopada 2023 (wcss.pl)
47th International Scientific and Technical Seminar CHEMISTRY FOR AGRICULTURE	-	-	-	47. Międzynarodowe Seminarium Naukowo-Techniczne Chemistry for Agriculture, Karpacz, 26-29 listopada 2023 (wcss.pl)
Centennial Celebration and Congress of the International Union of Soil Sciences	-	-	-	IUSS2024 ABSTRACT BOOK.pdf - Dysk Google
RSC Advances	ISSN: 2046-2069	Yes	YES	Brassica carinata and Camelina sativa oils as renewable raw materials for producing viscoelastic polyurethane foams
E-Abstract Book, 5th International Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety - FoodTech 2024", 16-18 October 2024, Novi Sad, Serbia, 101-101	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_4964
Zbornik Radova, 65. Savetovanje Industrije Ulja Proizvodnja i Prerada Uljarica, Herceg Novi, 23-28. Jun 2024, Montenegro, 117-124.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_4704
E-Abstract Book, 5th International Congress "Food Technology, Quality and Safety - FoodTech 2024", 16-18 October 2024, Novi Sad, Serbia, 208-208.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_4958
Book of Abstracts, 9th Congress on Plant Protection, 25-28 November 2024, Zlatibor, 123-124.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_5167
Zbornik rezimea, 12. Kongres o korovima i savetovanje o herbicidima i regulatorima rasta, 23-26.09.2024, Veliko Gradište, Srbija, 77-77.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_5692
Industrial Crops and Products, 227, 120773	ISSN: 0926-6690	Yes	Yes	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2025.120773
Zbornik Radova, 66. Savetovanje Proizvodnja i Prerada Uljarica Sa Međunarodnim Učešćem, 22-27. Jun 2025, Herceg Novi, Montenegro, 26-31.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_5495
Foods, 14(13), 2244.	EISSN 2304-8158	Yes	Yes	https://doi.org/10.3390/foods14132244
Book of Abstracts, 5th International Symposium for Agriculture and Food (ISAF 2025), 8-10 October 2025, Skopje, North Macedonia, 249-249.	-	Yes	Yes	https://hdl.handle.net/21.15107/rcub_five_r_5696
Sustainable Futures	SFTR-D-25-03277	YES	YES	https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5434834